

POLYMERS 2026 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

FROM DESIGN TO END-OF-LIFE IN CIRCULAR VALUE CHAINS: A WORKSHOP ON SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE BIO-BASED POLYMERS.

Key takeaways and presentations

Polymers
2026

KEY TAKEAWAYS

VISS

KEY TAKEAWAYS

INTRODUCTION

Organised by three European projects - ANIPH, ViSS and PHANTASTIC - the workshop took place in Lisbon on 9 April, within the Polymers 2026 International Conference.

The event brought together leading European research projects, industry actors, and policy experts to address one of the most pressing challenges in the transition to a circular economy: the development and deployment of safe and sustainable bio-based polymers.

Across sessions, a common narrative emerged: while bio-based and biodegradable plastics hold significant promise as alternatives to fossil-based materials, their successful implementation requires a systemic approach. This includes material design aligned with end-of-life scenarios, integration of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) principles, robust assessment methodologies, and alignment with evolving EU policy frameworks.

The workshop highlighted the importance of connecting innovation across the value chain—from raw material sourcing and polymer synthesis to processing, application, and environmental fate—while ensuring that sustainability, safety, and circularity are embedded from the earliest stages of development.

SESSION 1 – EUROPEAN INNOVATION LANDSCAPE & SSBd POLYMERS

This session provided an overview of the current European innovation ecosystem in bio-based polymers, showcasing several Horizon Europe projects addressing packaging and agricultural applications.

The **BIO4PACK cluster** (ViSS, REBIOLUTION, MAGNO and STOPP) showcased solutions for sustainable packaging, focusing on replacing fossil-based plastics, improving recyclability and biodegradability, and integrating circularity and safety considerations from the design phase.

The **agriculture-focused cluster** (PHAntastic, ViNNY and BioVIVE) highlighted the development of biodegradable polymer-based solutions for agricultural applications, including mulch films, delivery systems for bioactive compounds, and alternatives to conventional agrochemicals, all aligned with SSbD principles and EU sustainability targets.

Finally, the **ANIPH & MAGICBIOMAT cluster** addressed challenges related to biodegradable materials in open and uncontrolled environments, promoting materials with controlled and safe biodegradation, supported by advanced testing methodologies and digital tools.

KEY TAKEAWAYS:

- Bio-based polymers are central to achieving EU circular economy and climate goals.
- Circularity must be designed from the outset, including feedstock selection and end-of-life pathways.
- Cross-project collaboration (clusters) is essential to maximise impact and avoid fragmentation.
- Agricultural and packaging sectors are key application areas with high innovation potential.

[GO TO SESSION 1](#)

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KEY TAKEAWAYS

SESSION 2 – FROM RESEARCH DATA TO SUSTAINABLE EXPLOITATION: POLICY AND IP FRAMEWORKS

This session focused on how research outputs can be effectively translated into societal and economic impact through strategic data management and policy engagement.

Speakers highlighted that research results are not only publications but also valuable assets such as datasets, models and digital tools. The challenge lies in balancing openness (Open Science requirements) with protection (IP and exploitation potential).

The importance of early-stage planning for data sharing and protection was emphasised, along with the need to align research outputs with policy priorities and stakeholder needs.

KEY TAKEAWAYS:

- Data management is a strategic tool for impact, not just a compliance requirement.
- Accessibility alone is insufficient—data must also be usable, interoperable and sustainable.
- Timing and strategy in data sharing are critical to maximise value and exploitation.
- Strong links between research projects and policy frameworks enhance long-term impact.

SESSION 3 – SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE-BY-DESIGN (SSbD): FROM FRAMEWORKS TO DIGITAL TOOLS

This session explored how SSbD principles are operationalised in practice, moving from conceptual frameworks to real implementation tools.

SSbD was presented as a holistic and preventive approach integrating safety, environmental, economic and social dimensions across the full life cycle of materials. Case studies (e.g. ViSS project) demonstrated how tools such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Social LCA can guide design decisions and enable iterative improvements.

The session also highlighted current gaps, particularly in social and economic assessment methodologies, and the need for practical, user-friendly tools to support decision-making.

KEY TAKEAWAYS:

- SSbD shifts innovation from reactive to preventive approaches.
- Lifecycle thinking is essential to identify environmental and social hotspots.
- Iterative design (design–assess–redesign) is key to achieving sustainability targets.
- Further development of social and economic assessment tools is needed.

 [GO TO SESSION 2](#)

 [GO TO SESSION 3](#)

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KEY TAKEAWAYS

SESSION 4 – ADVANCED BIO-BASED POLYMERS: PROCESSING, SCALE-UP AND DIGITALISATION

This session addressed the transition from laboratory research to industrial application, focusing on processing technologies, scale-up challenges, and digital tools.

Presentations showed advances in nanoencapsulation systems, polymer compounding, and digital twins for packaging systems (e.g. MAGNO project). These innovations enable better control over material properties, functionality and lifecycle performance.

A key message was that scalability and processability remain major challenges for bio-based polymers, requiring optimisation of materials, processes, and supply chains.

KEY TAKEAWAYS:

- Bridging the gap between lab-scale innovation and industrial deployment is critical.
- Digital tools (e.g. digital twins) enhance decision-making across the value chain.
- Processing and material performance remain key bottlenecks for bio-based polymers.
- Integration of functionality (e.g. controlled release, smart packaging) is a growing trend.

SESSION 5 – BIODEGRADATION IN OPEN ENVIRONMENTS: METHODS, APPLICATIONS AND ASSESSMENT

The final session focused on biodegradability as an end-of-life solution, particularly for applications where material recovery is not feasible.

Speakers highlighted that biodegradability must be carefully assessed under realistic environmental conditions, as performance varies significantly depending on the context (soil, marine, freshwater). Standardisation and harmonised testing methodologies were identified as critical needs.

Advanced approaches, including AI-based predictive models (e.g. ANIPH), demonstrated the potential to accelerate material development by predicting biodegradability, toxicity and performance.

KEY TAKEAWAYS:

- Biodegradability is a valuable solution for specific applications, not a universal answer.
- Environmental conditions strongly influence degradation behaviour.
- Standardised and comparable testing methods are essential.
- Digital and AI tools can significantly accelerate sustainable material design.

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KEY TAKEAWAYS

CONCLUSIONS

The workshop clearly demonstrated that achieving safe and sustainable bio-based polymers requires a systemic, interdisciplinary and lifecycle-oriented approach.

INNOVATION MUST BE SUPPORTED BY:

- Integrated frameworks such as SSbD
- Strong collaboration across projects and sectors
- Alignment with policy and regulatory developments
- Advanced tools for assessment, modelling and decision-making

These elements are essential to ensure that bio-based polymers can effectively contribute to Europe's transition towards a circular, climate-neutral and pollution-free economy.

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CONFERENCE PRESENTATIONS

Polymers
2026

SESSION 1

EUROPEAN INNOVATION LANDSCAPE & SSbD POLYMERS

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European Innovation Landscape, Safe and Sustainable by Design Polymers

Guest Speakers:

Dr. Carmen Fernández

Spain

PhD in Chemical Engineering
Head of Coordination &
Project Management | CETEC

Dr. Alejandra Pita

Spain

PhD in Chemistry
Senior Researcher | IDENER

Dr. Yannik Matt

Germany

PhD in Chemistry (KIT)
Lab Team Leader | BASF

Dr. Milad Mosallaei

Finland

PhD in Printed Electronics
Research Scientist | VTT

INTRODUCTION to BIO4PACK CLUSTER

**BIO4
PACK**
Cluster

VISS

MAGNO

Stopp

REBIO3TION

BIO4PACK Cluster!

- The BIO4PACK Cluster brings together four Horizon Europe projects under five shared objectives.
 - Replacing fossil-based plastics with **bio-based materials**.
 - Designing **packaging for circularity** from the start.
 - Ensuring **safety and transparency** for people and the planet.
 - Harnessing **smart technologies** to enhance traceability and recycling.
 - Contributing to **European standards and policies** that promote sustainable packaging.
- Together, these projects drive Europe's green transition in food packaging.
- Cluster activities enable knowledge and experience exchange across Horizon Europe projects to maximize impact.

About the Speakers

- Dr. Carmen Fernández Ayuso, CETEC, Spain (**VISS**)
 - Dr Carmen Fernández Ayuso is Head of Coordination and R&D Management at CETEC, the Plastics and Footwear Technology Centre of the Region of Murcia, Spain. She holds a PhD in Polymers and has over 15 years of experience in plastics research, with a strong focus on biopolymers, recycling, circular economy, and innovation for industrial uptake. She is actively involved in the coordination of European and national R&D projects and works closely with companies and research organisations on sustainable polymer solutions.
- Dr. Yannik Matt, BASF, Germany, (**REBIOLUTION**)
 - Dr. Yannik Matt holds a B.Sc. and M.Sc. in Chemistry from the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), followed by a PhD in Chemistry at KIT. His doctoral research focused on the development of building blocks for three-dimensional organic frameworks and included a research stay at the University of Edinburgh. Dr. Matt is currently working at BASF SE, where he serves as a Lab Team Leader specializing in polyaddition and polycondensation processes for specialty polymers. In addition to leading a team, he acts as Work Package Leader for Synthesis and Blending within the Rebiolution Project, driving innovation in advanced polymer materials.
- Dr. Alejandra Pita Milleiro, IDENER, Spain (**MAGNO**)
 - Alejandra Pita holds a PhD in computational chemistry and works as a Senior Researcher at IDENER, a Spanish RTO focused on applying AI across sectors to deliver more efficient and sustainable solutions. She is part of the coordination of the MAGNO project and leads the development of its digital twin.
- Dr. Milad Mosallaei, VTT, Finland (**STOPP**)
 - Dr. Milad Mosallaei is a Research Scientist at VTT with a background in Materials Science (M.Sc.) and Printed Electronics (D.Sc.). His expertise spans polymer science, plastic compounding, recycling, and comprehensive characterization of polymeric materials, with a strong focus on advancing circular and sustainable solutions for plastics and food packaging.

**BIO4
PACK**

Viability, safety and sustainability of PHBV value chain for food packaging applications

Polymers Conference 2026. Workshop on Safe and Sustainable BioBased Polymers

Carmen Fernández Ayuso

Head of Coordination and R&D Management (CETEC).

c.fernandez@ctcalzado.org

UK Research
and Innovation

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Project Name: ViSS. Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications

Project start/end: September 2023/ August 2027

Coordinator partner and contact: CETEC, Carmen Fernández Ayuso coordinationviss@ctcalzado.org

Project website: <https://viss-project.eu/>

Project LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/viss-project/>

THE NEED: TO DEVELOP SUSTAINABLE ALTERNATIVES TO FOSSIL-BASED PLASTICS

One of the most promising biobased polymers is **the polyhydroxyalkanoates family, the PHAs**: produced by microorganisms and have excellent biodegradation properties.

Within PHAs family, highlights the **PHBV copolymer** (poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)). **It can modulate its properties according to the comonomer content (the hydroxyvalerate content).**

However, PHBV has some challenges to overcome:

- the PHBV **high production costs** mainly due to high costs of feedstock.

Current commercial PHBV has low 3HV content (2-3%), due to PHBV production requires costly precursors to increase the 3HV content, and thus commercial PHBV has **problems on the processability** (narrow processing window, slow processing cycles) and it is necessary to blend the PHBV with other polymers for industrial applications, hindering the biodegradation.

VISS: From food industrial residues to high performance food packaging

PROMISING RESULTS: TOWARDS INDUSTRIAL VALIDATION

DEMO 1- ViSS PHBV Production plant

Poultry residues
hydrolysis unit

Bioreactors room

Tangential
filtration

Evaporation

Extraction

✓ Construction and start up on going

PROMISING RESULTS: TOWARDS INDUSTRIAL VALIDATION

DEMO 1- ViSS PHBV Production plant

PHA type	Properties	Values
Y1000P PHBV* (1-2% 3HV)	Tensile strength	39 MPa
	Elongation at break	3,8%
CETEC PHBV (10-15% 3HV)	Tensile strength	28,3 MPa
	Elongation at break	4,0%
CETEC PHBV (20-30% 3HV)	Tensile strength	21,7 MPa
	Elongation at break	21,3%
CETEC PHBV (>30% 3HV)	Tensile strength	13 MPa
	Elongation at break	230%

(* TDS data for commercial PHBV grade)

<https://shop.helianpolymers.com/products/enmat-y1000p-phbv-pellets>

Going beyond the state of the art

- ✓ PHBV with high 3HV content
- ✓ PHBV safely formulated (SSbD)

PROMISING RESULTS: TOWARDS INDUSTRIAL VALIDATION

- **DEMO 3 – semiflexible packaging** (cast sheet extrusion)
- **DEMO 4 – flexible packaging** (film blowing extrusion)

First pilot-scale tests completed - Viss Project

VISS

HOME PROJECT NEWS & EVENTS RESOURCES

Home > News and Events >
First pilot-scale tests completed for VISS PHBV biopolymer production

First pilot-scale tests completed for VISS PHBV biopolymer production

Propagroup SpA and Helian Polymers BV collaborate on initial trials to validate processes for VISS PHBV

▪ Expected Project results

- Sustainable production of a PHBV range with high 3HV content (>10% 3HV) using residues as feedstocks.
- PHBV safe and sustainable formulation for flexible and semiflexible food packaging applications (mesh bags, bags, envelopes, trays).
- Biodegradability and mechanical recyclability of PHBV products demonstrated.
- Adoption of the ViSS value chain under a SSbD framework.

▪ Expected Project outcomes

- Reduction of CO₂ emissions: ↓57.3% the CO₂ emissions per kg of polymer in comparison with fossil based counterparts.
- Contribution to circularity, using residues as feedstocks and recirculating processes by-products: recirculating 288,95kt of biomass.
- Less toxicity materials: VISS plastic packaging manufactured upon non hazardous substances, avoiding the use of, at least 2,200 ton of hazardous substances.
- Enhance the consumers awareness about biobased plastics and the market acceptability.

VISS

Thank you

coordinationviss@ctcalzado.org

DISCOVER MORE AT:

viss-project.eu

 @VISS_project

 VISS project

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Novel biodegradable, **RE**cyclable, **BIO**-based and safe plastics
with enhanced circuLar properties for food packaging and
agricUltural applicaTIONS - **REBIOLUTION**

Polymers 2026 Conference, Lisbon

REBIOUTION

The Context

In agriculture, plastic mulch films are used to improve crop growth, save water, and reduce the need for chemicals. However, there is a risk of residual mulch film being left in the field during farming activities, especially when the film is too thin and hard to recover.

The agricultural plastics market accounts for 3.2% of the total plastic demand. As the world's food supply is expected to increase by 50% by 2050.

Executive Summary

- Project Name: ReBIOLution
- Project Start / End: 06/2023 – 12/2026
- Coordinator: Dr. Kai O. Siegenthaler, BASF SE, kai-oliver.siegenthaler@basf.com
- Project Website: www.rebiolution-project.eu
- Project LinkedIn: REBIOLUTION_project
- Project Target: 100% Bio-based and biodegradable polyesters and blends based on FDCA for paper coating applications (food paper packaging) and film applications (e.g. agricultural mulch films) with TRL 7-8.

Objectives

Develop fully bio-based, biodegradable and recyclable plastics for paper food packaging and agricultural films

Raw material sourcing from annually renewable sources

Assess the behaviour of the polymer blends and final bioplastic-based products in different EOL scenarios

Biodegradable in home and industrial composting, soil and aquatic environments

Enhancing circularity in applications where mechanical recycling is not possible – food paper packaging and agricultural films

Recyclable and safe to use

Project Overview

Project Partners

avantium

- Production of FDCA with Avantium's YXY® technology
- Legal framework

- Synthesis, scale-up and compounding of FDCA-based polyesters and blends.
- Biodegradation studies
- Film blowing studies

- Communication & Dissemination
- LCAs

REBIOLUTION - 101082040

Project Partners

- Paper coating trials
- Examination of properties

- Production of coffee cups and food trays
- Testing of cups and trays

- Printing techniques
- Repulping trials

REBIOLUTION - 101082040

Project Partners

- Composting trials
- Ecotoxicity tests

- Biodegradation in open water
- Method development
- Present @Polymers 2026

- Enzymatic hydrolysis
- Biodegradation in soil

REBIOLUTION - 101082040

Project outcomes and current status

▪ **Process and Application:**

- ✓ >500 kg FDCA produced and delivered to BASF
- ✓ Laboratory synthesis of ~ 30 polyesters with „Design of Experiment“ approach → Two final polyesters
- ✓ Polyester scale up to >750 kg & Polyester blending: Several hundred kilograms
- ✓ Extrusion Paper Coatings: Several kilometers of coated paper boards
- ✓ Film Blowing: >600 meters of blown mulch films
- ✓ Conversion of coated paper into coffee cups and trays
 - Evaluating repulping in lab and pilot scale
 - Investigate recycling strategies
 - LCA & Policy recommendations

▪ **Biodegradation:**

- ✓ Enzymatic hydrolysis of polyesters & soil degradation
- ✓ Biodegradation of polyesters under controlled composting conditions (EN 13432)
 - Concluding studies on biodegradation in soil, limnic and marine environment

REBIOUTION

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@ReBIOlution_pr REBIOLUTION_Project

MAGNO

Transforming EU food systems with innovative
strategies for sustainable packaging

Funded by the
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Europe's transition to climate neutrality and circularity is strongly dependent on how materials are produced, used, and managed

Packaging is a critical hotspot:

Represents **44%** of total plastics use in Europe

Recycling rates remain below the EU target of **55%** by 2030

At the same time, packaging is essential for food protection:

Ensures food quality and safety

Helps reduce food loss and waste across supply chains

Dual Challenge

Reduce material use and environmental impacts (e.g. waste, pollution)
&
Maintain or improve food preservation performance

- Project name (ID, budget): MAGNO (ID: 101135258, € 4M)
- Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-7 - Strategies to prevent and reduce plastic packaging pollution from the food system
- Project Start / End: 01/2024 – 06/2027
- Coordination: Dr. Alejandra Pita, Mr. Ignacio Fernández-Pacheco, Dr. Luis Acevedo
- Contact email: alejandra.pita@idener.ai
- Project Website: <https://magno-project.eu/>
- Project LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/magno-eu-project>

Criteria for strategies to prevent and reduce plastic packaging pollution from the food system:

- Innovative renewable and recyclable and/or biodegradable materials
- Design for circularity to reduce material consumption and increase reuse and recycle (physical and/or chemical design)
- Substitution of harmful substances in packaging formulations
- Smart solutions to monitor food quality and extend product shelf life

Specific objectives:

- Identify effects and impacts of littered plastic food packaging
- Develop and validate innovative business strategies
- Include government and society in food packaging system loop

The project focuses on the whole **food packaging value chain**, starting from raw materials production up to waste management – and back

Our goals are:

- Identify effects and impacts of food packaging **production**, **use** and **end of life**, with a particular focus on plastics
- Develop innovative **circular business strategies** and validate these with an **ecosystem Digital Twin**
- Include **public**, **private sectors** and **consumers** in food packaging system loop

Ecosystem Digital Twin (eDT)

- AI-powered knowledge pipeline
- First operational simulation modules developed: Product design, Manufacturing, Logistics, Shelf-life, End-of-life scenarios

Materials & Design Innovations

- Identified **11 bio-based alternatives** (e.g. PLA, PHAs, PBS)
- Assessed **10 packaging design trends**
- Highest impact strategies: Mono-materials, Reusable packaging, Waste-stream utilisation

Health & Environmental Impact

- Mapping of **micro- and nanoplastics (MPs/NPs)** impacts
- Assessment of ecosystem effects (marine & terrestrial)
- Evaluation of human exposure routes: ingestion, inhalation, dermal

End-of-Life & Value Chain Analysis

- Identification of **sustainability hotspots** in the plastic value chain
- Analysis of EU waste collection and sorting systems
- Evaluation of **mechanical and chemical recycling capacities**

Consumer & Stakeholder Engagement

- 31 industry interviews across the value chain
- Survey of **102 European consumers**
- Key insight: **attitude-behaviour gap** (price, functionality, safety dominate decisions)

MAGNO

Transforming EU food systems with innovative
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EU_STOPP Project

POLYMERS 2026 Conference

Milad Mosallaei (D.Sc.)
VTT Technical Research Center of Finland
09.04.2026

Strategies to prevent and reduce plastic packaging
pollution from the food system

Funded by the European Union

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Swiss partner funded by

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Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Agenda

- Introduction
- Overview of the STOPP project
- Challenges in food packaging
- STOPP solutions and opportunities
- Summary

Sustainable growth with research and development

VTT is a visionary research, development and innovation partner for businesses and society and one of Europe's leading research organisations.

We bring together people, businesses, science and technology to solve the world's biggest challenges and create sustainable growth, jobs and well-being.

2,390

employees

1,100

customers

296 M€

operating income

Plastics processing & characterization at VTT's Polymer Pilot: From laboratory to pilot scale

- Lab-scale melt processing
- Demonstration and piloting
- Testing and characterization
- Compounding
- Thermoforming
- 3D filament production
- Injection moulding
- Film processing & coating
- Extrusion foaming
- Particle foaming
- Micro-pelletizing
- Pre- and post-processing
- Analytical equipment (NMR, TG/MS, XRF, GC-FID, GC/MS, FT-IR, UV-VIS, HPLC)
- Mechanical characterization (Tensile & impact properties etc.)
- Thermal/mechanical/morphological characterization (DSC, TGA, MFI, DEA, WAXS/SAXS, HDT, TPS, rheology)
- Microscopy (SEM/EDS, optical microscopy, AFM)
- Spectroscopy (FTIR, UV/VIS, NMR)

STOPP Project Factsheet

- Project number: 101134958
- Project name: Strategies to prevent and reduce plastic packaging pollution from the food system
- Project acronym: STOPP
- Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01
- Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-7
- Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
- Granting authority: European Research Executive Agency
- Start date: 1 January 2024
- End date: 31 December 2026

Project Partners

NACIONALNI INŠTITUT ZA BIOLOGIJO
NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF BIOLOGY

GreenDELTA

Overview of the STOPP Project

STOPP develops science-based strategies to make food packaging circular, safe, and sustainable.

Key STOPP Objectives

- To analyze the plastic impact on diverse ecosystems, more precisely, create a report and gap analysis on how littered plastic from food packaging can affect the environment and ecosystems. (WP2)
- Supporting the transition of key stakeholders towards alternative circular solutions in food packaging systems by identifying their needs and motivations and creating practical tools. (WP3,6)
- Developing future-fit sustainable business model blueprint for packaging value chain including new materials, recycling and reusing scenarios. (WP3, 4)
- Increasing recycling, from the collection and sorting practices, so here for instance we are producing recommendations to improve collection and sorting. (WP5, 6)
- Consumer studies and awareness campaigns to engage over 10,000 European consumers in topics such as reusable packaging or behaviour change to improve awareness, acceptance and uptake. (WP6,7)

What Makes Recycling of Food Packaging Difficult?

Essential for food safety but difficult to recycle

Challenges:

- High contamination
- Complex structures
- Collection system variability
- Limited feasibility of reusable packaging
- Consumer behaviour challenges

STOPP's Responses to Challenges

- Safe food contact recyclate
- Monomaterial packaging
- STOPP Evidence-Based Recommendations to Improve Collection Systems
- Reuse systems innovations
- Societal engagement and behavioral shifts

Summary

Challenge	Opportunity
Contamination	<p>Safe Food Contact Recyclates</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Advanced PP decontamination processes• NIAS/migration safety frameworks• Cleaner feedstock via eco design & sorting improvements
Complex Packaging Structures	<p>Monomaterial Packaging Solutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• PP based monomaterials replacing multilayers• Improved barrier properties via processing technologies• High compatibility with established recycling streams
Collection & Sorting Variability	<p>Enhanced Design for Recycling (DfR)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Packaging designed to match real sorting/collection systems• Evidence based DfR rules under development (RecyClass)• Structure simplification → more consistent recycle quality
Limited Feasibility of Reuse Systems	<p>Reuse System Innovations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Accelerated ageing & wear testing• Optimized washing/return logistics (digitalization, automation)• Removable sealing layers enabling scalable reuse
Consumer Behaviour Challenges	<p>Societal Engagement & Behavioural Shifts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Large scale behavioural studies• Field pilots validating behaviour change strategies• Multi Actor Community & brand owner bootcamps for better uptake

Stopp

Thank you very much!

 STOPP PROJECT

 @STOPPPROJECT

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European Innovation Landscape, Safe and Sustainable by Design Polymers

Guest Speakers:

Dr. Carmen Fernández

Spain

PhD in Chemical Engineering
Head of Coordination &
Project Management | CETEC

Dr. Asier Fernandez

Spain

PhD in Polymers
Senior Researcher | CTME

Dr. Margarida M. Fernandes

Portugal

PhD in Materials Science/Biotechnology
Senior Researcher & Research Group
Leader | University Minho

All three projects are funded under the same Horizon Europe call: **HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-34 — Advanced (nano and bio-based) materials for sustainable agriculture** | Duration: 2024–2028

PHAntastic

PHA (polyhydroxyalkanoates)

PHA-based mulch films & growth foams

- PHA compounded with bio-based active ingredients
- Controlled release of bio-fertilisers & plant protection products
- Full soil biodegradation | TRL6 field validation (Spain & Netherlands)
- 15 partners, 7 countries | Coord. by CETEC (Spain)

ViNNY

Biodegradable nanoencapsulation matrices

Stimuli-responsive biopolymer carriers for viticulture

- Stimuli-responsive biopolymer nanoformulations
- Vine-derived bioactives encapsulated as biopesticides & biofertilisers
- Agrotextile impregnation as second delivery platform
- 19 partners | Coord. by Univ. Minho (Portugal)

BioVIVE

Bioplastic films, biochar & sprayable biopolymers

Biodegradable delivery systems for horticultural biocontrol

- Complementary biodegradable polymer platforms
- Biological agents for pathogen control in horticulture
- Validated in carrots, strawberries & tomatoes
- 15 partners | Coord. by Univ. of León (Spain)

What Do These Projects Share?

Key convergences across PHAntastic · ViNNY · BioVIVE

Same EU Call & Topic

All funded under HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-34 — advanced bio-based materials for sustainable agriculture

Biodegradable Delivery Systems

Bio-based and biodegradable carriers: PHA-based films/foams, nanoencapsulation platforms, biochar and biopolymer coatings

Agricultural Applications

Delivery of bio-fertilisers, biopesticides and plant protection products. Field validation in real crop settings across Europe

Safe & Sustainable by Design

SSbD principles embedded in R&D. Environmental, ecotoxicological and LCA assessments throughout the projects

Reducing Agrochemical Dependence

All three aim to significantly reduce the use of synthetic fertilisers and pesticides, supporting the EU Farm to Fork targets

Regulatory & Stakeholder Engagement

Shared challenges in regulatory preparedness, market uptake and co-design with farmers and value chain actors

Meet the Speakers

PHAntastic · ViNNY · BioVIVE presentations

PHAntastic

Dr. Carmen Fernández Ayuso

Head of Coordination & R&D Management

CETEC — Plastics & Footwear Technology Centre, Murcia, Spain

PhD in Chemical Engineering with over 15 years of experience in plastics and bioplastics research. Coordinator of the PHAntastic project. Expert in biopolymers, recycling, circular economy, and European R&D project management.

 phantastic-project.eu

ViNNY

Dr. Margarida M. Fernandes

Tenure Assistant Researcher

CMEMS, University of Minho, Portugal

PhD in Materials Science (Textile Engineering). Coordinator of ViNNY. Expert in sustainable functional materials, nanotechnology, stimuli-responsive systems, and antimicrobial technologies for agriculture and biomedical applications.

 projectvinny.eu

BioVIVE

Dr. Asier Fernández de Añastro

Researcher in Sustainable Materials

CTME — Centro Tecnológico de Miranda de Ebro, Spain

Expert in advanced materials spanning energy storage technologies and sustainable polymer development. Works on biodegradable and thermoplastic biopolymer compounding for agricultural and sustainability-driven applications.

 biobive.eu

Bioactive Polymers
for Healthier Soil

PHANTASTIC PROJECT OVERVIEW

PHA-BASED INNOVATIVE AGRICULTURAL SOLUTIONS
TO DELIVER BIO-BASED FERTILIZERS AND PLANT PROTECTION PRODUCTS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- **Project Name:** PHA-based innovative agricultural solutions to deliver biobased fertilisers and plant protection products
- **Project start/end:** September 2024/ August 2028
- **Coordinator Contact:** Carmen Fernández (CETEC) coordinationphantastic@ctcalzado.org
- **Project website:** <https://phantastic-project.eu/>

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CONTEXT

THE NEED: TO DEVELOP SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE PRODUCTS

There is a pressing need to **reduce the environmental, social and economic impacts of agriculture products.**

PHAntastic faces relevant challenges:

• **Agrochemicals, fertilisers and pesticides**, are widely used to increase crops productivity. However, they cause relevant impacts, **contaminating** soil, water, food value chain, and human health.

Delivery systems (e.g., controlled release fertilizers, polymer coated pesticides) allow modulating the agrochemicals application and enhance efficiency, contributing to reduce application volumes and associated harmful impacts. However, most of them incorporate fossil-based and non-biodegradable plastics.

• **Fossil based and/or not completely biodegradable plastics** used in agriculture such as **mulch films and growth foams** causing important **environmental impacts** (e.g., plastic pollution) and **socio-economic impacts** (e.g., public disapproval, economic costs of removal).

Current **compostable/biodegradable polymer alternatives** are generally blends of oil and bio-based polymers (e.g., PLA, TPS, PBAT) that do not always completely degrade in the soil.

PHANTASTIC SOLUTION

PHANTASTIC GOES BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART BY DEVELOPING TWO INNOVATIVE DELIVERY SYSTEMS FOR ACTIVE BIOPRODUCTS INSPIRED BY WIDELY USED AGRICULTURAL PLASTICS: MULCH FILMS AND GROWTH FOAMS

PHANTASTIC SOLUTION

PHANTASTIC MULCH FILMS DELIVERY SYSTEMS

POLYMER MATRIX

Active bioproducts **incorporated into PHA** matrix for release after crop cycle

COATING

Active bioproducts integrated in **nanocapsules** for controlled release during plant growth

PHANTASTIC SOLUTION

PHANTASTIC GROWTH FOAMS DELIVERY SYSTEMS

1
Initial growth stages in the nurseries. Impregnation solution embedded into porous structure of the foam will support plant growth during its initial growth stages in nurseries.

2
After transplant into the final location. PGPR and soil bacteria will further biodegrade the foams, releasing all the active bioproducts embedded in the polymer matrix into the soil.

3
After complete biodegradation of the foams, the plants will benefit from remaining active bioproducts and a healthy soil microbiota.

PHANTASTIC ADVANCEMENTS

Selection of active BIOPRODUCTS families, to be included in PHANTASTIC delivery systems

- **Plant-based amino acids and hydrolyzed proteins**

- **Peptide/Oligosaccharide-based elicitors**

- **Algae extracts**

- **PGPR's rhizobacteria**

PHBV polymers from agrifood residues produced

PHBV 10-30% 3HV: higher processability and flexibility at higher 3HV content.

PHBV characterisation and stabilisation

P_HAntastic

Safe and sustainable formulation and compounding with other commercial PHAs to obtain compounds for the mulch films, foams and capsules.

REGULATORY BENEFITS

The Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/2770 of 15 July 2024 amend the Regulation (EU) 2019/ The **EU Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR) REG 2009/1009**. This regulation defines biodegradable mulches as a new category of fertilizing product.

An EU fertilising product may contain polymers where the purpose of the polymers is:

- (a) to control the water penetration into nutrient particles and thus the release of nutrients (in which case the polymer is commonly referred to as a 'coating agent'),
- (b) to increase the water retention capacity or wettability of the EU fertilising product, or

From 17 October 2028, the polymers referred to in point 1(a) and (b) shall be:

- (a) **polymers that are the result of a polymerisation process that has taken place in nature, independently of the process through which they have been extracted and which are not chemically modified substances within the meaning of Article 3, point (40), of Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006; or**
- (b) **polymers that are biodegradable in accordance with the criteria set out in Appendix 1 to this Annex.'**

https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202402770

Our mulch films will biodegrade completely into the soil and will fertilise the soil being aligned to this regulation. This ensures they don't leave behind microplastics, making them a sustainable alternative to conventional plastic mulches.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

- **Coordinator Contact:** Carmen Fernández (CETEC) coordinationphantastic@ctcalzado.org
- **Project website:** <https://phantastic-project.eu/>
- **Subscribe to our Newsletter:** <https://phantastic-project.eu/contact/#Newsletter>
- **Follow us in LinkedIn:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/phantastic-project/posts/?feedView=all>

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POLYMERS 2026
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

08 - 10 APRIL 2026
LISBON, PORTUGAL

Vine-Derived Bioactives as Encapsulated Biopesticides for Sustainable Viticulture

Margarida M. Fernandes, Mariana P Fernandes, Catarina Roque,
Beatriz Cardoso

Universidade do Minho
Escola de Engenharia

1. Microbiome from grapes

Yeasts

Bacteria

B. cinerea Bacteria 1

P. expansum Bacteria 2

Fungi

HBLA und Bundesamt
Klosterneuburg
Wein- und Obstbau

In vitro screening the activity of new BPs
actives to inhibit growth of ESCA fungi

Splitting the grape parts

Extraction procedure

Antifungal activity

Antibacterial activity (CFUs reductions)

Controls

Variety: Tinta Roriz

Stem
5HE

Botrytis (inhibition %)

6%

Penicillium (inhibition %)

10.87%

S.Aureus (log reduction)

2.0338

E.Coli (log reduction)

0.3370

Variety:

Souvignier

Leaves
10HE

16%

21.9%

2.5822

-0.2940

Fertilizers

Biochar

Rich in C,P and K

What about amonia (N)?

Meat industry

Blood: High content of nitrogen

Organic waste from meat industry: blood, rumen content, stomach content,..

Aim: Using blood residues to load the fresh biochar with nutrients

Biochar enriched with N-rich blood

Release of $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ in water

Valorization of waste water treatment plants sludge, vineyards, meat industry

**Bio-oil (biopesticide)
Condensation line**

BioFertilizer

SCREENING FOR ANTIFUNGAL POTENTIAL

BIO-OIL 350

Tested against 5 fungi

Tendency to have a dose-dependent effect

C. gleosporioides was inhibited at 24.5 and 49 mg/mL

Different letters indicate statistical differences among the same fungus

Bio-oil nanoparticles loaded with grape cane extract

Preparation method, size and surface evolution

Size and surface evolution

Size: ~400 nm → ~230 nm
PDI: ~0.30 → ~0.15
Zeta-potential: -30 mV → -12 mV → -5 mV

- ✓ Progressive size, PDI and zeta-potential reduction
- ✓ Changes in interfacial organization over time

Bio-oil nanoparticles loaded with grape cane extract (INDESA-SAS)

Antibacterial activity

Antibacterial activity (\log_{10} CFU/mL reduction)

A- *Staphylococcus aureus*

B- *Xylophilus ampelinus*

C- *Pectobacterium parmentieri*

D- *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*

Gram-positive: *S. aureus*

Gram-negative: *X. ampelinus*, *P. parmentieri*, *A. tumefaciens*

Strong antibacterial activity

- ✓ Observed against all tested microorganisms
- ✓ **Stronger against *S. aureus***

Alginate and alginate/chitosan encapsulating *W. anomalous* HN1

	Mean diameter (cm ± SD)	Mean weight (mg ± SD)
Empty alginate beads	0.380 ± 0.08	40.14 ± 5.28
	0.200 ± 0.05	4.28 ± 0.29
Alginate beads encapsulating <i>W. anomalous</i>	0.420 ± 0.04	39.8 ± 4.29
	0.230 ± 0.04	5.80 ± 0.56
Chitosan-coated alginate beads	0.436 ± 0.08	41.81 ± 4.37
	0.200 ± 0.02	3.92 ± 0.44
Chitosan-coated alginate beads encapsulating <i>W. anomalous</i>	0.411 ± 0.09	43.50 ± 2.90
	0.255 ± 0.09	5.3 ± 0.79

Mean diameter and weight of empty alginate and chitosan-coated alginate beads and encapsulating *W. anomalous* by ionotropic gelation method. Shaded (grey) corresponds to measurements of beads in their hydrated state, whereas unshaded (white) corresponds to measurements in their dry state. Values are expressed as mean ± SD (n = 20)

Hydrated Particles

Optical microscopy images of hydrated beads: empty alginate beads (scale bar: 500 μm) (A); chitosan-coated alginate beads (scale bar: 1 mm) (B); alginate beads encapsulating *W. anomalous* (scale bar: 1 mm) (C); and chitosan-coated alginate beads encapsulating *W. anomalous* (scale bar: 1 mm) (D).

Alginate and alginate/chitosan encapsulating *W. anomalous* HN1

Encapsulation efficiency and viability after encapsulation

	EE (%)
Alginate/Chitosan-coated alginate beads	99.99 ± 0.002

$$EE (\%) = \frac{CFU_i - CFU \text{ in supernatant}}{CFU_i} \times 100$$

- *W. anomalous* showed **~100% encapsulation efficiency**, indicating almost total cell retention within the alginate matrix;
- **Encapsulation did not impair cell viability** or enzymatic activity, confirming **effective protection by the alginate matrix**.
- Yeast cells were encapsulated in alginate prior to chitosan deposition; **Chitosan formed only an external layer and did not affect encapsulation efficiency or cell viability**.

Alginate and alginate/chitosan encapsulating *W. anomalus* HN1

In vitro antagonistic activity of the encapsulated *W. anomalus* yeast by dual culture assay

- **Hydrated beads showed antifungal effects, while dehydrated beads completely lost activity.**
- Alginate beads produced ambiguous inhibition due to fungal contamination under non-sterile conditions.
- **Chitosan antifungal activity required hydration** to enable electrostatic interactions with fungal cell surfaces.

- Chitosan-coated alginate beads consistently restricted fungal growth.
- Beads loaded with *W. anomalus* showed stronger inhibition than empty chitosan–alginate beads.
- **Antifungal activity resulted from a complementary effect between hydrated chitosan and encapsulated *W. anomalus*.**

EFFECTIVE BIOACTIVES

Bio-oils and plant extracts exhibited strong antifungal and antibacterial activity.

ENHANCED DELIVERY

Nanoparticles improved stability, protected bioactives and allowed controlled release, increasing their persistence and efficacy.

EFFICIENT & SAFE

Encapsulation of *W. anomalus* yeast achieved ~100% efficiency and preserved cell viability and antagonistic activity.

CIRCULAR & SUSTAINABLE

Valorization of waste streams (grape by-products, meat industry residues, biochar, sludge) supports a circular bioeconomy and reduces environmental impact.

VINNY's strategy supports the transition toward a more sustainable, efficient and environmentally responsible viticulture, paving the way for viable alternatives to synthetic pesticides

Thank You!

Questions?

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Universidade do Minho
Escola de Engenharia

AMBi
Applied Mechanobiology &
Biointerfaces Laboratory

09/04/2026

BIOdegradable delivery systems for plant pathogens control of horticultural crops through **Bio-actiVE** agents

-BioBIVE-

Funded by
the European Union

Asier Fernández de Añastro

Programme:
Horizon Europe

Coordinator:
University of León

Focus:
Sustainable agriculture and biodegradable plant protection solutions.

Progress:
1,75 years of 4 years

Consortium

This is **BioBIVE**:

- 6 countries
- 16 Partners:
 - 3 Universities
 - 5 Research centers
 - 6 SMEs
 - 1 Cooperative
 - 1 Large enterprise
- 3 “hubs”

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Background and Problem

The challenge

European agriculture still relies heavily on synthetic pesticides to control plant diseases. Although effective, this dependence has significant costs for ecosystems, human health, and long-term soil sustainability.

The EU Policy Response

The European Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy aim to cut pesticide use by 50% by 2030, requiring new, effective, and environmentally responsible plant protection approaches.

Environmental pollution

Pesticide runoff pollutes water and soil, harming ecosystems and long-term land quality.

Biodiversity loss

Chemical inputs disrupt soil microbiomes, pollinators and wider ecological communities, undermining the foundations of sustainable food production.

Human health risks

Prolonged exposure to agrochemical residues poses neurotoxic and immunotoxic risks to farmworkers, rural communities and consumers alike.

BIOBIVE solution

BioBIVE tackles these problems by creating **biodegradable delivery systems** that use natural substances to protect plants. By combining biology and advanced materials, the project aims to give farmers a reliable and effective alternative to synthetic pesticides.

Bioactive agents:

- basic substances
- biocontrol microorganisms,
- phlorotannin-rich extracts

Nettle (Urtica sp.)

Horsetail (Equisetum sp.)

Bacteria

Brown algae (Giant kelp)

Delivery platforms:

- biodegradable mulch films
- sprayable mulch films
- Biochar and (their combinations)

BIODEGRADABLE MULCH FILMS

Extrusion

SPRAYABLE MULCH FILMS

Sprayable water solutions

BIOCHAR PRODUCTION

Pyrolysis technology

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Target crops

The EU produces a wide range of fresh vegetables and fruit.

In 2022:

- 2 million hectares cultivated
- 59,8 million tonnes harvested fresh vegetables.

BioBIVE focuses on three crops of **major economic significance** across the EU, selected for their relevance to key production regions within the consortium and their vulnerability to soil-borne and foliar pathogens.

Tomato

Carrot

Strawberry

Biodegradable mulch film

Polymer-based films incorporating **bioactive agents** that degrade naturally in the soil following the growing season. Designed to suppress soil pathogens whilst improving moisture retention.

✓ Extrusion compounding

PBAT

Poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate)

A biopolymer that enhances flexibility

PBSA

Poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate)

A biopolymer that provides good biodegradability

- ✓ Good balance between mechanical and biodegradable properties
- ✓ Characterization
- ✓ Biodegradability tests

Biodegradable mulch film

Work-flow

Extrusion

Chitosan

Horsetail

Biochar

Film-blowing

Chitosan containing film

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- ✓ Good balance between mechanical and biodegradable properties
- ✓ Characterization ongoing
- ✓ Biodegradability tests ongoing

Sprayable mulch film

Liquid formulations applied directly to the soil surface, forming a thin **biodegradable barrier**. This approach offers greater flexibility for growers, particularly in established crops or complex terrain, and enables direct delivery of biocontrol agents to the soil.

- ✓ *Polysaccharides*
- ✓ *Come from nature, available, biodegradable...*
- ✓ *Most of them, water soluble*
- ✓ *Due to their specific intrinsic chemo-physical properties can get water insoluble films.*

Biochar serves as a **porous, high-surface-area** carrier for bioactive agents, providing controlled slow-release whilst simultaneously improving soil structure, water-holding capacity and microbial habitat (creating a durable, multifunctional amendment).

Biochar from pine - observation by SEM pine. From left to right – 1 mm, 200 μm and 50 μm.

- ✓ Good ability to bind nutrients.
- ✓ Compatibility with other delivery systems.
- ✓ Controlled surface area.

Future work and conclusion

3 Delivery systems has been successfully manufactured.

Mulch film

Sprayable film

Biochar

Biological tests on petri dish

Field test are ongoing to measure the release of the substances and their effect on the soil

Industrial scale

**THANK YOU
VERY MUCH**

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European Innovation Landscape, Safe and Sustainable by Design Polymers

 Aniph & mAgIcbiomat **CLUSTER** introduction

Common objectives of ANIPH & MAGICBIOMAT

- ✓ Develop bio-based materials and products with reduced environmental impact
- ✓ Enable safe and sustainable biodegradation in specific environments
- ✓ Design materials for circularity
- ✓ Develop innovative manufacturing processes for programmable biodegradation
- ✓ Apply AI and digital tools to optimise product lifecycle and performance
- ✓ Contribute to information and labelling systems for end-of-life options

Addressing a global challenge

- Plastic waste leakage in open environments is a **global pollution issue**
- Low recycling rates require **alternative end-of-life solutions**
- Biodegradability can provide **safe solutions where waste management is not feasible**

Cluster contribution

- ✓ Supports **EU Green Deal & Circular Economy Action Plan**
- ✓ Promotes **bio-based alternatives to fossil-based plastics**
- ✓ Enables **safe and sustainable circular systems**

European Innovation Landscape, Safe and Sustainable by Design Polymers

Guest Speakers:

Mrs. Cristina Blaya

Spain
Industrial Engineer
R&D Project Manager | CETEC

Dr. Yuanyuan Chen

Ireland
PhD in Biodegradable coronary stents
Senior Researcher | University TUS

About the Speakers

- **Mrs. Cristina Blaya, CETEC, Spain (ANIPH)**

Cristina Blaya is Project Manager at the coordination team at CETEC. She holds a Master's in Industrial Engineering from the University of Valencia, where she specialized in materials and biomaterials. She facilitates collaboration among multidisciplinary teams, monitor progress against technical objectives and deadlines, and manage resources to foster innovation, sustainability, and knowledge transfer.

- **Dr. Yuanyuan Chen, University TUS, Ireland (MAGICBIOMAT)**

Dr Yuanyuan Chen is a Principal Investigator (PI) in the Polymer, Recycling, Industrial, Sustainability and Manufacturing (PRISM) programme at the Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest (TUS). Her expertise includes biopolymer synthesis, processing, modification, degradation and recycling. She is currently coordinating a European consortium to programmable control the degradability of biopolymers (MAGICBIOMAT HE101181381), a European Innovation Council project in developing bio-based and biodegradable polyesters (Bio2PEs HE 101221903), and a Research Ireland & Horizon Europe co-funded project “Traceless” in developing biodegradable tree-supporting products (SFI22/NCF/HE/1142).

Avoiding the negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts

ANIPH

Polymers 2026, Lisbon

9th April

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ANIPH PROJECT OVERVIEW

Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts

Funded by
The European Union

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- **Project Name:** Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts
- **Project start/end:** January 2025 / December 2028
- **Coordinator Contact:** Carmen Fernández (CETEC)- coordinationaniph@ctcalzado.org
- **Project website:** <https://aniph.eu/>
- **Project LinkedIn:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/aniph-project>

ANIPH gathers a strong and complementary consortium

CONTEXT

THE NEED: TO DEVELOP SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE BIOBASED AND BIODEGRADABLE PLASTIC PRODUCTS

- The **proliferation of waste** littered in open environments and the subsequent pollution from harmful substances it releases, **especially from plastic materials**, has escalated into a **global emergency**.
- **Some products** due to their nature (litter prone), or specific use scenario (e.g. agricultural mulch films, products used in humanitarian contexts), might be **hard to collect at their end of life**, suggesting the use of biodegradable materials as a solution.
- In this context, the **biodegradability of materials and products for targeted applications could offer viable end-of-life solutions**, provided biodegradation occurs safely and sustainably, whether in open environments or under controlled conditions.

CHALLENGES

Biobased and biodegradable plastic products (BBpPs) are emerging as a crucial part of the solution. However, they faces several **challenges to ensure their safe and sustainable deployment.**

1

Ensuring lifecycle alignment with circular economy principles

Renewable feedstock
Circular production processes

2

Tailored design from production to end-of-life routes, being aligned with appropriate disposal or recycling.

Polymers design with safe biodegradation including safe substances is key for biodegradable plastic used in open environments

3

Reproducibility of biodegradation tests standards → no consideration of environmental factors and materials properties affection biodegradation process

Need to be complemented by standard specifications, e.g. setting pass levels for each environmental compartment

4

Establishing an enabling environment and preventing misleading claims

Fostering adoption of biobased and biodegradable value-chains: SSbD and reliable labelling

ANIPH SOLUTION

HOW ANIPH OVERCOME THESE CHALLENGES

1

ANIPH enhances circularity by using renewable agrifood waste as feedstock, recycling waste within production, minimizing industrial waste through optimized processes

2

ANIPH programs PHA biodegradation:

- Production stage.
- Formulation and compounding.
- -Manufacturing of the tailored products

3

ANIPH uses a robust 3-tier testing system to accurately assess biodegradation, material lifespan, environmental persistence, and overall ecological impact.

4

ANIPH fosters a supportive ecosystem by developing Safe and Sustainable by Design approaches and labeling for bio-based, biodegradable plastics.

ANIPH SOLUTION

ANIPH SOLUTION

USES CASES

WOUND DRESSING: In ANIPH, the wound dressings are single-use, made from **biobased and biodegradable** PHBV and designed for **humanitarian settings**, with **programmed biodegradation** to ensure safe breakdown in natural environments.

ITS PACKAGING: The packaging developed in ANIPH is a **monomaterial flexible film** designed to serve as a **recyclable barrier** against moisture and contamination. It is produced using **cast or blown extrusion**, enhanced with PHA-based **coatings** and **sustainable medical additives**, offering a **circular alternative** to multilayer, non-recyclable packaging.

ANIPH DIGITAL EMPOWERMENT AND FUTURE IMPACT

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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MAGICBIOMAT - Manufacturing guiding tool for circular and programmed biodegradable materials under open environment conditions

€3.8 million
4-year Project
Started on 1st Jan 2025

No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1 (Coordinator.)	Technological University of the Shannon	TUS	IE
2	Università degli Studi di Padova	UNIPD	IT
3	Organik Kimya	OK	TR
4	Digiotouch OU	DIGI	EE
5	Centre Technique Industriel de la Plasturgie et des Composites	IPC	FR
6	ISOTECH	ISOTECH	CY
7	University of Sheffield	USHEFFIELD	UK

Demonstration of key applications

APPLICATIONS WITH PROGRAMMED BIODEGRADABILITY

Short term application

Biodegradable acrylic coated single use paper trays – Roll coating

Short term application

BB biodegradable agricultural mulches – Blown film extrusion

APPLICATIONS OF CIRCULAR BB BIODEGRADABLE PRODUCTS

Reuse

BB biodegradable reusable laundry washing liquid bottle – Extrusion blow moulding

Remanufacturing

BB biodegradable agricultural mulch remanufactured into bin bags – Ultrasonic sealing

Recycling

Mechanical recycling of BB biodegradable polymers – Twin-screw extrusion

Recovering multiple components – Solvent borne and water borne acrylic adhesive

Controlled environment: industrial compost, soil, fresh water/sea water

Open environment biodegradation across EU

Blend Input

Environment
Industrial compost

PLA wt%
80.00

PBAT wt%
20.00

PBS wt%
0.00

TPS wt%
0.00

Additive family
Bioadditives

Bioadditive category
Chitosan

Bioadditive wt%
0.00

Total (polymers + additive): 100.0%

Thermal-ready presets in local data include PLA 100/0/0/0 and PBAT 0/100/0/0.

Magicbiomat AI-powered blend demo (Prototype)

Nearest-neighbor predictions from existing repository datasets

Predictions

Mechanical (predicted)

E (MPa)
962.7

UTS (MPa)
47.66

Elongation at break (%)
35.9

Standard: ISO_527_3, ISO tensile (partner file)

Source: saved regression model `poly2_ridge`

TPS is included in the model input, but the current TUS mechanical training set contains only TPS=0 blends, so TPS effects are low-confidence/extrapolative.

Thermal (predicted)

Tm PLA (C): **152.5**

Standards in nearest evidence: Not available

Model Confidence

Distance (avg): 9.43

Confidence: **High**

Additive input: **Chitosan (0.0%)**

Biodegradation standards: **ASTM D5338, ISO 14855**

Biodegradation Curve

Polymers
2026

SESSION 2

FROM RESEARCH DATA TO SUSTAINABLE
EXPLOITATION: POLICY AND IP FRAMEWORKS

Polymers
2026

From Research Data to Sustainable Exploitation: Policy and IP Frameworks

Guest Speakers:

Mrs. Roberta Mallia

Italy

MA in Accounting, Financial Management
and Control

Innovation expert | ICONS

Mrs. Suzan Naz Uzel

Belgium

BA in Political Science and International Relations
MA European Political and Governance Studies

Policy Officer | REVOLVE

Dr. Salima Abu Jeriban

Civil and Chemical Engineer

Research Executive Agency | EC

About the Speakers

- **Mrs. Roberta Mallia , ICONS, Italy (ANIPH)**

Roberta Mallia is an innovation expert, with consolidated professional experience in the development and management of innovation programs in several industries, with a focus on the energy transition and healthcare fields. She holds a Master in Accounting, Financial Management and Control from Bocconi University. In her professional experience, she applied innovation management in different contexts, but mainly within corporates, working on the definition of innovation strategy, the implementation of innovation projects and the development of new business models propositions. She has additional experience in the startup ecosystem, supporting aspiring entrepreneurs in developing their innovative solutions, and in venture capital. In ICONS, she has the role of Business Innovation Officer, supporting the definition of exploitation strategies and innovation management for research projects. She is the lead of exploitation in ANIPH project.

- **Dr. Suzan Naz Uzel, REVOLVE, Belgium (PHAntastic)**

Suzan Naz has a Bachelor's in Political Science and International Relations, and a Master's in European Political and Governance Studies. Previously, she worked as a contributing writer for a US-based think tank; and at the United Nations Development Program on the environment, climate change and sustainability topics. She currently works as a Policy Officer at REVOLVE, supporting EU-funded projects on sustainability. Prior to that, she worked as a research officer at the 89 Initiative Belgium, co-authored a research report where she focused on climate action and the interaction between civil society and political actors at the European Union level.

- **Dr. Salima Abu Jeriban, (Project Advisor)**

Civil and Chemical Engineer from the École Polytechnique de Louvain (UCL). Horizon Europe Project Adviser at REA (European Research Executive Agency). Primarily involved in research and innovation projects relating to the circular economy. Has worked for 18 years in the field of mobility and transport in Europe. Specialisms: European projects, Transport, Mobility, Urban planning, Intelligent Transport Systems, Prospective and strategic studies of mobility projects, Research, Innovation, Circularity, Development, R&D, R&I.

ICONS

Avoiding the negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts

Managing research data for sustainable exploitation: accessibility, sustainability, and IP protection

Polymers Conference, April 9th 2026

Roberta Mallia, ICONS

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The European Union

ICONS – About us

Building the bridge between research and society via public communication, business and social innovation

Funded in 1999, ICONS has **+ 25 years experience** in communication & dissemination, social innovation, exploitation and innovation management of EU-funded projects.

ICONS has been involved in **more than 130 EU funded research & innovation projects** covering multiple domains.

Through an **integrated, impact-driven and measurable approach** to maximise impacts of European research & innovation projects on society.

Why managing data matters

- **Collaborative research projects are at the core of the European R&I system.**
- These projects don't generate only publications, but also **high-value datasets, digital tools, and complex data-driven outputs.**
- Results are not just outputs: they are **key assets** and play a central role in **innovation, impact, and future exploitation.**
- **Strong open science requirements**, promoting accessibility and reuse of research results in line with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

How can we ensure openness, while preserving the potential value of the results we generate?

The Open Science challenge

Similar patterns across different projects:

- Data is shared because it is required
- But its potential value is not always assessed
- Decisions are taken late in the project

What often happens:

- Share too early or too much → opportunity loss
- Protect too much → limiting reuse

OPEN \neq UNPROTECTED

A clear data sharing strategy is essential in order to avoid losing part of its value

Value dimensions of research data

In many projects, we often focus on making data accessible. But **accessibility alone does not create value**. The value of research data depends on **multiple dimensions**:

ACCESSIBILITY	Can others access it?
INTEROPERABILITY	Can others use it?
SUSTAINABILITY	Will it remain usable over time?
PROTECTION	Can you control its use?

The question is not only whether to share data, but how to make it usable, sustainable, and strategically managed.

This is what creates impact!

Not all data is equal – some examples

Each type of data requires a different approach to sharing and protection

Experimental datasets

Interoperability: standards and formats
Sustainability: repository and update

A dataset that is open but cannot be reused is not impactful

Models / Algorithms / Tools

Interoperability: integration with other systems
Protection: access control and ownership

If a tool is reusable but not protected, its value may be transferred to others

Co-created data

Accessibility: limited
Sustainability: governance agreements

Long-term usability depends on clear (shared) ownership and agreements

Strategic planning for data protection

How do we decide what to share, and when?

- Does it have potential value beyond the project?
- Can it be easily reused or replicated?
- Is there a partner interested in exploiting it?

Strategic questions!

**Strategic planning is key to ensure long-term sustainability.
It determines whether data can become impact (and not output).**

Strategic planning for data protection

Different answers lead to different strategies:

SCENARIO	SUGGESTED APPROACH
Low value, low reuse	Open early
High value, high reuse	Protect first, share later
Strategic interest (partner)	Coordinate access and timing

Timing is often more important than openness itself!

Open vs exploitation is a trade-off:

IF YOU PRIORITIZE	YOU GAIN	YOU RISK
Openness	Visibility, reuse	Loss of control
Protection	Commercial potential	Limited dissemination

Tools for data protection

IP protection measures

Directive 96/9/EC on the legal protection of databases:

- **Copyright:** protects the structure of the database, only if it is original.
Automatic protection.
- ***Sui generis* right:** protects the contents of the database, when there is substantial investment
Needs registration.

Data Management Plan (DPM)

Central tool to anticipate and manage the balance between openness and protection, **if used with a strategic approach.**

Useful only if it **defines what, when, and how to share** and it supports decisions. Not if it remains a formal document.

→ Needs early-stage planning

Key takeaways

- Open Access requirements **do not prevent the protection** of research data
- **Not all data should be shared**, and not immediately
- **Accessibility alone does not create value**: data needs to be also usable and sustainable
- **Strategic data management** is necessary to balance IP protection and openness
- **Timing is a strategic decision**: early decisions can shape long-term impact

Strategic management of research data is essential to enable sustainable exploitation and long-term impact

THANK YOU!

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Bioactive Polymers for Healthier Soil

A science-based pathway to sustainable agriculture in Europe

Suzan Naz Uzel, REVOLVE

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Context and challenge

Modern agriculture in Europe heavily relies on synthetic fertilisers, pesticides, and plastic-based materials.

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What are agrochemicals?

Agrochemicals are chemical products, mainly fertilisers and pesticides, used in agriculture to maintain and increase productivity.

However, the excessive use of agrochemicals causes severe impacts, contaminating wildlife, water, food, and endangering human health.

Biodegradable

A substance that can be broken down naturally by microorganisms into water, carbon dioxide, and biomass.

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Existing “biodegradable” alternatives often fall short. Many contain fossil-based components or require industrial composting conditions that are not representative of real agricultural environments.

As a result, residues can persist in soils, contributing to long-term environmental burdens. There is a clear need for materials that are both functional in the field and truly biodegradable under natural soil conditions.

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The PHAntastic Solution

The PHAntastic project addresses these challenges by developing delivery systems based on polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), a class of bio-based and fully biodegradable polymers produced through microbial fermentation.

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PHAs, or polyhydroxyalkanoates, are **natural, biobased & biodegradable plastics** made by microorganisms from organic waste. They are a **promising alternative** to fossil-based traditional plastics used in farming. PHAs completely break down in soil and water without harming the environment.

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These materials are engineered into:

1

Mulch films

2

Growth foams

By embedding active compounds such as amino acids, microelements, and beneficial microbes, PHAntastic systems support plant growth while gradually releasing nutrients as the material biodegrades.

This approach reduces reliance on synthetic agrochemicals and eliminates persistent plastic residues.

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Unlike conventional plastics or some bioplastics (e.g., PLA-based materials), PHAs are naturally metabolised by soil microorganisms, integrating into existing biogeochemical cycles.

This makes them particularly suitable for open-environment agricultural applications.

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Beyond material degradation, PHA-based systems actively contribute to soil health.

As PHAs biodegrade, they act as a carbon source for soil microorganisms, stimulating microbial activity and potentially enhancing biodiversity.

This can improve key soil functions such as nutrient cycling and organic matter formation.

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PHAntastic materials are designed to release embedded nutrients and bioactive compounds gradually.

This leads to:

Improved nutrient use efficiency

Reduced fertilizer application rates

Lower risk of nutrient leaching and runoff

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Regulatory and Standardisation Challenges in Europe

Despite technological advances, the regulatory landscape for soil biodegradable materials in Europe remains fragmented.

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Gaps in Standards

Policy Implications

As the EU advances its Soil Strategy and Circular Economy Action Plan, there is increasing recognition of the need for:

- Field-based validation methods
- Clear biodegradability criteria in soil
- Alignment between innovation and regulation

PHAntastic as a Solution

PHAntastic directly addresses both scientific and policy challenges by combining robust material innovation with real-world validation.

- **Science-Based Credibility**

Demonstrated biodegradation in diverse European field conditions

Integration of material science, microbiology, and agronomy

- **Environmental Performance**

Elimination of persistent plastic residues

Contribution to soil health and ecosystem functioning

- **Scalability and Adoption**

Compatibility with existing agricultural practices

Potential for industrial-scale PHA production

Alignment with EU sustainability and climate objectives

Conclusion

Transitioning to sustainable agriculture requires solutions that address both productivity and environmental integrity.

PHA-based systems developed within the PHAntastic project offer a credible, scalable pathway by replacing conventional plastics, reducing agrochemical dependence, and enhancing soil health.

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Thank you for your attention

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About PHAntastic

With the official title “PHA-based iNnovative agriculTurAI Solutions to deliver bio-based ferTIlisers and plant protection produCts”, the PHAntastic project uses polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) to develop biodegradable mulch film and growth foam delivery systems, reducing the need for synthetic agrochemical inputs and non-biodegradable polymers. The PHA-based delivery systems containing active bioproducts will be demonstrated in European horticultural and tree nursery settings.

Coordinated by the CETEC and comprising 15 partners from 7 countries, this 4-year (2024-2028) €7.4M Horizon project contributes to a secure food supply chain and a reduced environmental impact of agriculture, boosting the sustainability, autonomy and competitiveness of vital EU value chains.

Get in touch

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Media Requests

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Maximising EU projects' synergies and policy impacts

**Workshop on Safe and Sustainable BioBased Polymers: from
design to end of life in Circular Value Chains**

9 April 2026

by Salima Abu Jeriban

Project Adviser

Research Executive Agency (REA) / European Commission

[#HorizonEU](#) / [Salima Abu Jeriban | LinkedIn](#)

Outline

- What is REA?
- Policy landscape – what is new?
- Maximising project synergies
- Projects4policy
- Upcoming opportunities

REA's responsibilities

Funding and managing EU projects under:

- Horizon Europe
- Horizon 2020
- Research Fund For Coal and Steel
- Promotion of agricultural products

Offering cross-cutting support for:

- Project evaluation
- Participant validation*
- Handling of expert evaluators
- Research Enquiry Service

* For Calls for proposals and Calls for tenders

Objectives

HORIZON-CL6-2022-CIRCBIO-02-03

Develop **sustainable biodegradable novel bio-based plastics** with improved functionalities and **enhanced end-of-life options**, ensuring overall environmental sustainability.

HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-7

Develop and implement **strategies to prevent and reduce plastic packaging pollution from the food system**, including improved design, use, and end-of-life management.

HORIZON-CL6-2024-CIRCBIO-01-5

Advance **bio-based materials and products with programmed biodegradation capability**, validated in **specific environments**.

Policy landscape – what is new?

- 2018 Commission adopts EU Plastics Strategy
 - 2019 Farm to fork strategy
 - 2019 Directive on Single-Use Plastics
 - 2020 EU circular economy action plan
 - 2021 Zero pollution action plan
 - 2022 Policy framework for biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics
 - 2023 Several initiatives on microplastics
 - **NEW** 2025 Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)
 - **NEW** 2025 EU bioeconomy strategy
 - **NEW** 2025 EU Clean Industrial Deal
 - **NEW** 2025 Revised SSbD Framework
 - **NEW** 2026 Package of measures to boost circular economy and strengthen Europe's plastic recycling
 - **NEW** 2026 Industrial Accelerator Act
- Upcoming:

- 2026 Circular Economy Act

Ongoing projects on plastics in cluster 6

Project Acronym	Project Title
SYSCHEMIQ	Demonstrator of systemic solutions for the territorial deployment of the circular economy in the Trilateral Chemical Region with a focus on plastic waste streams Quality for Recycling
R3PACK	Reduce, Reuse, Rethink PACKaging: towards novel fiber-based packaging and reuse schemes uptake
BUDDIE-PACK	Business-driven systemic solutions for sustainable plastic packaging reuse schemes in mass market applications
ViSS	Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications
REBIOLUTION	Novel biodegradable, REcyclable, BIO-based and safe plastic polymers with enhanced circuLar properties for food packaging and agricUltural applicaTIONS
CircSyst	Circular Systemic Solutions for Plastic, Packaging, Bio-Waste, and Water
ACTPAC	A Complete Transformation PAth for C-C backboned plastic wastes to high-value Chemicals and materials
MAGNO	Conquering new strategies to prevent and reduce packaging pollution
STOPP	Strategies to prevent and reduce plastic packaging pollution from the food system
BioPhenom	Multifunctional biophenols for safe and recyclable materials
ANIPH	Avoiding the Negative Impacts produced by Plastic materials in Humanitarian contexts
RETAIN	Demonstrating circular value chains for complex plastics via collection, reuse, repair, remanufacture, recycling and ecodesign of PVC tarpaulins
EcoPlast	Empowering Circular Operations in the Automotive Plastics Value Chain
Magicbiomat	Manufacturing guiding tool for circular and programmed biodegradable materials under open environment conditions

+ 3 new GAPs

Project synergies

What unites us?

BIO4PACK is a cluster formed by four Horizon Europe projects – STOPP, MAGNO, VISS and REBIOLUTION – working together to revolutionise food packaging by making it greener, smarter, and truly sustainable. Know more about each initiative on its respective website:

www.viss-project.eu
www.stopp-project.eu
www.magno-project.eu
www.rebiolution-project.eu

Login

SSbDHub

Knowledge and Data Exchange Platform

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Project focus

Bio-based polymers & plastics

Status

In progress

Type of project

Select Value

Feedstock origin

Select Value

Feedstock type

Select Value

Biorefinery location

Select Value

Results (15)

Sort by

A-Z

Export results

BIOntier

The need for renewable, eco-friendly materials is driving the increasing demand for bio-based composites. The sector is however facing many challenges...

Project focus: Bio-based polymers & plastics

In progress

BIOPYRANIA

The European automotive and energy industries are facing the challenge of creating sustainable alternatives to fossil fuel-based products with a low...

Project focus: Bio-based polymers & plastics

Projects4Policy

What information do EU policymakers need?

Robust, evidence-based results and insights generated by projects

Validated and scalable solutions, with demonstrated transferability across contexts

Quantified economic and environmental/climate performance, benchmarked against state-of-the-art technologies and virgin materials

Identification of R&I gaps and remaining barriers

Clear, actionable and coherent policy recommendations

Where to start?

There are **3 main steps** for researchers to effectively feed into policy:

1. Understand policy context

- **Monitor** policy developments relevant to the project's field
- **Understand needs** at EU, national, regional and local levels
- **Know when** input is needed
- Identify **relevant project results**
- **Connect** with relevant policymakers

2. Join forces

- **Establish relationships** with stakeholders in similar or complementary fields
- Identify **synergies** & potential areas of collaboration

3. Plan for policy impact

- Identify **issue** and **purpose** of sharing results
- Identify **target audience**
- Make relevant **recommendations**
- Focus on linking **results** to the policy issue
- Start early and plan for **timely inputs**
- Choose the right **channel**

Policy impact opportunities

- **EC public consultations / Call for evidence**
 - Currently, all relevant ones are closed.
 - Recently closed - Rules on single-use plastics and fishing gear
 - Recently closed Plastic waste – EU-wide end-of-waste criteria
- **(Joint) policy briefs**
 - Final project events / cluster meetings
 - Contributing to high profile events (e.g. Green week) / already existing platforms (CE Stakeholder Platform, JRC Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy, SSbD Hub etc.)
- **Feedback 2 policy requests from REA**
 - ENV 2025: Sustainable products
 - RTD 2026: evidence from R&I projects on public procurement, extended producer responsibility, end of waste criteria, recycled and bio-based content, EoW criteria and Transnational/regional hubs
 - ENV 2026: Circularity and digital tools – traceability

Guidance to share scientific evidence with policymakers

- [Sharing scientific evidence with policymakers: A starter kit for EU funded research & innovation \(R&I\) projects](#)
- [Sharing scientific evidence with policymakers: Guide on writing policy briefs for impact](#)
- [10 steps to reach and inform policymakers](#)
- [10 Tips for Researchers: How to achieve impact on policy](#)
- [Smart4Policy: Reflect about your work on policy!](#)

Upcoming stakeholder / synergies opportunities

- 21 April – CBE JU Networking Event, Brussels
- 22-23 April – European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform annual conference, Brussels
- 19-22 May – EUBCE 2026 - 34th European Biomass Conference and Exhibition, The Hague
- 20-21st October – Global Bioeconomy Summit 2026, Dublin, Ireland

Upcoming EU calls for proposals

Call/Topic	Title	Opening date	Deadline date
CL6-2026-01-CIRCBIO-01	Improving circularity of multilayer flexible plastic food contact packaging	17 Apr 2026	17 Sept 2026
CL6-2026-01-CIRCBIO-07	Advancing the European bio-based innovation enabled by biotechnology and biomanufacturing concepts	17 Apr 2026	17 Sept 2026
CL6-2026-01-CIRCBIO-10	Bio-based innovation in society: supporting the sustainable way of living	17 Apr 2026	17 Sept 2026
CL6-2027-01-CIRCBIO-03	Developing novel recycling technologies for complex plastic materials applying biotech solutions	20 Apr 2027	22 Sept 2027
CL6-2027-01-CIRCBIO-09	Increasing the circularity of bio-based sector: upcycling and recycling for higher value and environmental benefits	20 Apr 2027	22 Sept 2027

Link to Info days - Cluster 6 Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment

<https://research-innovation-community.ec.europa.eu/events/2s2Xz6DhSgsazEcBuxo0Pm/>

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Polymers
2026

SESSION 3

SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE-BY-DESIGN (SSbD): FROM FRAMEWORKS TO DIGITAL TOOLS

Polymers
2026

BLOCK 2: Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD): From Frameworks to Digital Tools

Guest Speakers:

Mrs. Alba Matamoros

Belgium

MA Economic Policy and Public Economics

Head of Project Coordination and Management & Senior R&D
Consultant | Kveloce

Mrs. Inka-Mari Sarvola

Finland

Master's degree in Agriculture and Forestry Science
Research Scientist | VTT

About the Speakers

- **Mrs. Alba Matamoros, Kveloce, Belgium (PHAntastic)**

Alba Matamoros is Head of Project Coordination and Management at Kveloce and Senior R&D Consultant specializing in circular economy and innovation. She holds a Master's in Economic Policy and Public Economics from the University of Valencia, with over seven years of experience managing Horizon Europe projects. She leads the implementation and assessment of sustainable bio-based polymer solutions, combining Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) frameworks with social impact and life cycle assessment methodologies.

- **Mrs. Inka-Mari Sarvola , VTT, Finland (viSS)**

Inka-Mari Sarvola is a Research Scientist at VTT specializing in life cycle assessment and carbon footprinting in agriculture and bio-based systems. She holds a master's degree in Agriculture and Forestry Science. Inka-Mari has contributed to European and Finnish research projects focused on cellular agriculture, biofuels, biopolymers, and biocarbon, advancing sustainability in diverse sectors. Her research interests focus on applying frameworks like Safe and Sustainable by Design and bridging the gap between reporting environmental impacts and acting on them.

Safe and Sustainable- by-Design (SSbD): From Frameworks to Digital Tools

Alba Matamoros

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www.kveloce.com
m

Joint workshop:

VISS

Agenda

BLOCK 2: Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD): From Frameworks to Digital Tools

15:00 -15:05	Introduction and opening	<i>Mrs. Alba Matamoros, KVC, Belgium</i>
15:05- 15:20	Safe and sustainable by Design framework	<i>Mrs. Alba Matamoros, KVC, Belgium</i>
15:20- 15:35	LCA supporting sustainable design development	<i>Mrs. Inka-Mari Sarvola, VTT, Finland</i>
15:35- 15:50	LCC and S-LCA in practice: the ViSS case study	<i>Mrs. Alba Matamoros, KVC, Belgium</i>
15:50 - 16:05	Interactive session. Q&A	<i>Mrs. Alba Matamoros, KVC, Belgium</i>

Safe and Sustainable- by-Design (SSbD): From Frameworks to Digital Tools

Safe and sustainable by Design framework

15:05-15:20 | Alba Matamoros, Kveloce

Historical Cases: Why SSbD Matters

Abestos

1930-1980

Cancer

Prohibition and withdrawal

CFCs

Chlorofluorocarbons

1930-1990

Ozone depletion

Global phase-out required

BPA

Bisphenol A

1960 – present

Endocrine Disruptors

Hidden health risks (retroactive restrictions)

...

PFAS? (forever chemicals)

UV filters?

Glyphosate?

Revolutionary Materials

Traditional innovation model

Common factor:

Used first → evaluated later → banned or heavily regulated

Reactive approach

Fix problems after they appear

*High costs for
remediation
Irreversible damage*

*Decades for
implementation
Loss of public trust*

SSbD Framework: From Reactive to Preventive

Product Life Cycle

Assessment

Detect issues at design stage

✓ Evidence-based redesign

Benefits: Anticipation · Responsible innovation · Long-term viability

What is SSbD framework?

A voluntary framework to integrate safety and sustainability considerations throughout the entire innovation process—from early design stages to end-of-life.

PREVENTIVE

Anticipate risks

Evaluate from design phase

BALANCED

No single dimension dominates

Seek viable solutions

HOLISTIC

Assess entire life cycle

Integrate multiple dimensions

Origin: EU Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (2020)

SSbD Dimensions: Three Pillars

Product life cycle assessment

Product life cycle perspective

SSbD evaluates the product/service impact across its entire lifecycle

Why? Hidden impacts often occur upstream (mining, processing) or downstream (disposal, recycling)

SSbD application steps

DESIGN PRINCIPLES

SSbD in practice: a real decision

Imagine you need to choose between two packaging materials:

Material A:

- 30% cheaper
- Lower carbon footprint
- Questionable labour practices in supply chain

Material B:

- More expensive
- Higher carbon footprint
- Strong social certifications

Which do you choose?

SSbD in practice: a real decision

Imagine you need to choose between two packaging materials:

Material A:

- 30% cheaper
- Lower carbon footprint
- Questionable labour practices in supply chain

Material B:

- More expensive
- Higher carbon footprint
- Strong social certifications

Which do you choose?

SSbD provides tools to make this trade-off transparent and data-driven

Safety assessment - Chemical and material safety

Chemical/ Material safety assessment

Intrinsic hazard

- Chemical properties & toxicity

Exposure assessment

- Occupational, consumer & environmental

Safety assessment

- Risk characterization of material

Process-Related Risk Assessment: Supply Chain

Production process selection

- Evaluate alternative pathways

Occupational risk

- Worker health & safety throughout supply chain

Process safety assessment

- Compare alternative processes

Integrated Risk Assessment

Combines intrinsic hazard properties of the chemical/material with exposure pathways (occupational, consumer, environmental) to characterize overall risk.

Additionally, evaluates process-related risks throughout the supply chain by comparing alternative production pathways to identify the safest route from design phase onwards.

Environmental sustainability assessment - Life cycle assessment (LCA)

Tier approach

- Low TRL → LCA screening (simplified)
- Medium TRL → Streamlined LCA (intermediate)
- High TRL → Full LCA

Economic sustainability assessment - Life cycle costing (LCC) & feasibility

Life-cycle cost structure

Internal costs

Organised by life cycle stage

Societal-LCC = Internal costs
+ Societal costs

Externalities monetisation

Social costs
• Monetary valuation of LCA results

Corporate benefits
• Savings for users
• Value of recycled materials

Benchmarking

Compare design options

Identify cost drivers

Identifying win-win situations and trade-offs

Sensitivity analysis

Social sustainability assessment – Social Life Cycle assessment (S-LCA)

LCA supporting sustainable design development

15:20-15:35 | Mrs. Inka-Mari Sarvola, VTT, Finland (**ViSS project**)

Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications

LCA supporting sustainable design development

Inka-Mari Sarvola and Katri Behm

VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.

9/04/2026

UK Research
and Innovation

Co-Funded by the European Union under Grant No. **101081931**

Safe and sustainable by design

Garmendia Aguirre et al. 2025. Safe and Sustainable by Design Chemicals and Materials - Revised framework.

Life Cycle Assessment

ISO standardized method

- What are the main environmental impacts?
- Which life-cycle stage is the main impact contributor?
- What are the hotspots?

Sustainability assessment of a chemical process

Sustainability assessment of a chemical process

Introduction to ViSS

Aim: to create a safe, sustainable, fully functional and highly replicable circular value chain of PHBV bioplastic

Follows Safe and Sustainable by Design framework

- Safety by IDENER
- Social sustainability by KVELOCE
- Environmental sustainability by VTT

First sustainability assessment M18

PP benchmark system

PHBV system

- Value chain up to raw PHBV
- Mass balances directly from technical partners (IRIS, CETEC, CETBIO)
- Impact factors for upstream emissions from ecoinvent 3.10
- Fossil PP from ecoinvent 3.10 database as benchmark

eSbD category	Aspect (Impact category)	Scaled values	
		Benchmark PP	VISS raw PHBV
Toxicity	ecotoxicity: freshwater	1	2926
	ecotoxicity: freshwater, inorganics	1	448
	ecotoxicity: freshwater, organics	1	29080
	human toxicity: carcinogenic	1	1788
	human toxicity: carcinogenic, inorganics	1	549
	human toxicity: carcinogenic, organics	1	1828
	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic	1	1021
	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic, inorganics	1	656
	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic, organics	1	4840
Climate change	climate change	1	783
	climate change: biogenic	1	4875
	climate change: fossil	1	485
	climate change: land use and land use change	1	597708
Pollution	acidification	1	825
	eutrophication: freshwater	1	630
	eutrophication: marine	1	3104
	eutrophication: terrestrial	1	1096
	ionising radiation: human health	1	485
	ozone depletion	1	599
	particulate matter formation	1	929
	photochemical oxidant formation: human health	1	577
Resource use	energy resources: non-renewable	1	384
	land use	1	7027
	material resources: metals/minerals	1	716
	water use	1	1828

Conclusions

- No improvements compared to fossil PP benchmark
- Drastically more emissions in all impact categories
- Identified a need to re-design/reduce the virgin chemical use
 - Enhance solvent recuperation
 - Reduce the total amount of solvents, especially in volatile fatty acid production
 - Improve yields in fermentation steps

eSbD category	Aspect (Impact category)	Scaled values	
		Benchmark PP	VISS raw PHBV
Toxicity	ecotoxicity: freshwater	1	2926
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	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic, organics	1	
Climate change	climate change	1	
	climate change: biogenic	1	
	climate change: fossil	1	
	climate change: land use and land use change	1	
Pollution	acidification	1	
	eutrophication: freshwater	1	
	eutrophication: marine	1	
	eutrophication: terrestrial	1	
	ionising radiation: human health	1	
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Resource use	energy resources: non-renewable	1	384
	land use	1	7027
	material resources: metals/minerals	1	716
	water use	1	1828

Conclusions

- No improvements compared to fossil PP

After submission of first iteration results, IRIS reduced the use of solvents.

ns in all impact
 design/reduce the virgin
 recuperation
 amount of solvents, especially
 d production
 fermentation steps

After redesigning on solvent usage

		Scaled values		SSbD score
		ViSS raw PHBV	PP	
Toxicity	human toxicity: carcinogenic	133	1	0
	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic	116	1	0
	ecotoxicity: freshwater	198	1	0
Climate change	climate change	70	1	0
Pollution	ozone depletion	42	1	0
	particulate matter formation	101	1	0
	ionising radiation	88	1	0
	photochemical oxidant formation	62	1	0
	acidification	121	1	0
	eutrophication: terrestrial	173	1	0
	eutrophication: freshwater	92	1	0
	eutrophication: marine	260	1	0
Resources	water use	307	1	0
	land use (soil quality index)	1322	1	0
	energy resources: non-renewable	33	1	0
	material resources: metals/minerals	179	1	0

Interim sustainability assessment M33

PP benchmark system

PHBV system

- Re-designed value chain up to raw PHBV
- Mass balances directly from technical partners (IRIS, CETEC, CETBIO)
- Energy balances from CETBIO and literature

- Impact factors for upstream emissions from ecoinvent 3.10
- Fossil PP from ecoinvent 3.10 database as benchmark

eSbD category	Aspect (Impact category)	Scaled values		
		First assessment ViSS raw PHBV	Interim assessment ViSS raw PHBV	PP
Toxicity	human toxicity: carcinogenic	133	25	1
	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic	116	42	1
	ecotoxicity: freshwater	198	13	1
Climate change	climate change	70	18	1
Pollution	ozone depletion	42	17	1
	particulate matter formation	101	14	1
	ionising radiation	88	344	1
	photochemical oxidant formation	62	16	1
	acidification	121	26	1
	eutrophication: terrestrial	173	26	1
	eutrophication: freshwater	92	22	1
	eutrophication: marine	260	27	1
	Resources	water use	307	41
land use (soil quality index)		1322	113	1
energy resources: non-renewable		33	20	1
material resources: metals/minerals		179	60	1

Conclusions

- 40-94% decrease in potential impacts (exc. ionising radiation) from Solvent redesign iteration while simultaneously the system boundary was expanded to cover energy consumption as well
- Still no improvements compared to fossil PP benchmark
- Redesign needed still to decrease the potential impacts to benchmark level

Fairness of benchmark

Fairness of benchmark

- In order to progress towards sustainable design, one must
 - quantify
 - measure
 - and have a target
- Many iterations, a snapshot of the situation at that point of development
- A comparison between low TRL and industrial benchmark may be a flaw in SSbD framework, but it is still a good push towards sustainable desing

Take home messages

- The whole (practical) point of implementing SSbD: design, assess, and re-design based on the results
 - Early identification of emission hotspots
 - Collaboration to make meaningful redesign
 - Timely redesign when changes are still technically and economically feasible
- LCA is a tool to guide the design to reach sustainability
 - A valid tool to success, not just a reporting burden

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Thank you!

Inka-Mari Sarvola

VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd

UK Research
and Innovation

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S-LCA and LCC in practice: the ViSS case study

15:35-15:50 | Alba Matamoros, Kveloce (**ViSS project**)

ViSS project: Safe and Sustainable PHBV Bio-based Polymers

PHAs & PHBV copolymer

100% biodegradable polymers from renewable sources. Excellent properties for food packaging

Expected Outputs

Demo plants for PHBV production
3 packaging product demos (*mesh bags, flexible packaging, semiflexible packaging, trays*)

Key challenges

1. High production cost
2. Processing difficulties
3. Limited mechanical recycling

SSbD: evaluate Safe & Sustainability

Integrate safety, environmental, economic and social dimensions from design phase to ensure responsible innovation

References used in ViSS

European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)

<https://www.h2020sunshine.eu/>
<https://www.surpass-project.eu/>
<https://iriss-sbd.eu/>

<https://iriss-sbd.eu/iriss/about-iriss>

Safe And Sustainable-By-Design

Estimated reading time: 4 minutes

Accelerating chemical innovation

Cefic and its members define Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) as an iterative process guiding innovation and market placement of solutions that are safe, and offer environmental, societal, and/or economical value. This includes new chemical materials, products, processes, and services, as well as the potential redesign of existing ones.

CEFIC: The European Chemical Industry Council

VISS Polymers 2026

<https://cefic.org/a-solution-provider-for-sustainability/safe-and-sustainable-by->

Design principles: social principles proposal

Proposal to follow Missimer's (Missimer, 2015) five principles for social sustainability

Initial exercise to set the scene for further reflexion and consensus

Essential to **consider the social aspects in the design principles** of the product

Health

- Avoid injury and illness (physical, mental or emotional)

Influence

- Foster people participation in shaping the social systems they are part of.

Competence

- Help people to learn and develop their individual competences.

Impartiality

- Avoid partial treatment of people.

Meaning-making

- Support the creation of individual meaning and co-creation of common meaning

Assessment of social sustainability in ViSS

D6.7 First sustainable by design assessment

Annex 2: Questionnaires to organizations in ViSS value chain for the So-LCA

Purpose & Confidentiality disclosures

This questionnaire is intended to gather the required information to perform the Social Organizational Life Cycle Assessment entitled in the ViSS project under the Task 6.4.

The data you provide through this questionnaire will only be used for the ViSS project purposes, under no circumstances will be passed on to third parties. This data will be managed by José Benedicto Royuela & the staff of SENIOR EUROPA S.L. (with commercial brand Kveloce). You can exercise your rights of access, modification or deletion of data by sending an email to jbenedicto@kveloce.com

Please include your name and surname: _____

Position in the organization: _____

General company information ²⁴ Please complete the following gaps with the organization information:

Last accounting year	
Total company workforce in the last accounting year	
Nº of injuries in the last accounting year	
Total number of hours worked by employees in the last accounting year	

Data collection from members of the ViSS value chain regarding social sustainability (consultation):

Results: interim sustainability assessment

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Fair competition	NEGATIVE	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour (question 7.2.3)	0	0	0	Cases opened by the National Commission for Markets and Competition at the national level	2024	The reference law is 1/2002, of February 21, on antitrust ⁵⁰ .
						5 (MU); 82 (ES) ⁵⁰		
Promoting social responsibility	POSITIVE	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility (question 8.1.2)	0	0	0	Companies that plan to implement CSR agreements/ guides in Spain	2024	Existence in the organisation of a CSR agreement.
						42% ⁵¹		
	POSITIVE	Suppliers SCR audit (question 7.2.5)	0	0	0	Percentage of companies with SCR policies and certifications 0.01% (n2989/N=3207580 companies ES) [39]; ≈1% [40]; MU: 41 Companies SCR 2024 ISO 9001 ⁵² PYMES That have sustainable buying policies: 20.6% ⁵³	2024	Recent grey literature was consulted for determining the number of companies formally integrating SCR within their supply processes
Supplier relationships (question 7.2.6)	POSITIVE	Suppliers' communication relationship (question 7.2.6)	4	4	6	29% (ES); ISO 14001: (ES 2018) >26000 orgs. ; total (ES 2014) 2413 [41] [42] [43]	2019, 2021	Likert scale: 1 to 6 (1: coercive communication to 6: very fluent communication)
Wealth distribution (question 7.2.8)	POSITIVE	Fair price definition	1	1	1	No data available		Existence of a policy for deciding a fair price.

CATEGORY	ASPECT	INDICATOR	SCORE	
Workers	Fair salary	Organisation average wage, per month	4	
	Working hours	Full-time staff	4	
	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Gender equality		2
		Health and safety	Occupational safety measures	3
		Lost time injury frequency rate	4	
		Presence of sufficient safety measures	4	
	Social benefits, legal issues, social security	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	4	
	Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Collective Bargaining Agreement	4	
	Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported	4	
Value chain actors	Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	4	
	Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	0	
	Supplier relationships	Suppliers audit	0	
	Wealth distribution	Suppliers' communication relationship	3	
Society	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Fair price definition	4	
	Contributions to economic development	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	0	
	Technology development	Total taxation per capita	4	
		Technology transfer	4	
		Investments in technology development/ transfer	2	
Local community	Access to material resources	Environmental management system	2	
	Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate	1	
		Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community	1	
	Safe and healthy living conditions	Promotion of community health	0	
	Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation	3	
		Number of meetings with community stakeholders	2	
	Local employment	Workforce hired locally	2	
		Spending on locally based suppliers	3	
	Secure living conditions	Security complaints by the community	4	

Design principles: economic principles proposal

Cost Efficiency

- Reduce production costs by optimising both fixed and variable costs

Resource Optimisation

- Minimise expenses associated with acquiring materials thanks to adopting efficient material usage practices

Equipment Lifecycle Management

- Evaluation of total expenditures, not just in terms of initial investment but over the entire lifespan

Installation and Operational Efficiency

- Optimise installation costs and design products with an emphasis on efficient operational processes.

Human Resource

- Consider the social impact by ensuring fair wages and reasonable working hours

Environmental Management

- Design products with a focus on minimising negative environmental consequences throughout their lifecycle.

Proposal grounded in current literature and the concepts outlined in the SSbD JRC frameworks

Initial exercise to set the scene for further reflexion and consensus

Design principles: economic principles proposal

ECONOMIC CATEGORIES		COST							PRICE AND MARKET								
Economic aspects		Product cost			Life cycle cost and externality cost				Market related criteria		Profitability analysis						
Economic indicators		Purchase cost	(Total) Production cost	Minimum selling price	Externality cost	Cost of waste treatment	Environmental taxes	Environmental subsidies	Externality cost	Willingness to pay	Product performance	Normalised added value	Profitability	Net present value	Added value	Payback period	Financial profit
Economic sustainability principles	Cost Efficiency																
	Resource Optimization																
	Equipment Lifecycle Management																
	Installation and Operational Efficiency																
	Human Resource																
	Environmental Management																
Sub-indicators		1	10	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Principles: JRC (2022), Robèrt et al. (2002) & Antwi-Afari et al. (2022) / Aspects: JRC (2022)

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Assessment of economic sustainability in ViSS

Raw material cost		Acquisition of waste stream input
Production cost (other inputs and operating costs)	Water	Water consumption cost for the facility and systems
	Energy	Energy consumption cost for the facility and systems (including: electricity, thermal energy and natural gas used in the production process)
	Carbon dioxide to air	Associated cost to emitted carbon dioxide during the manufacturing process - not included yet in the LCA
	Transport	Cost of freight, cartage, transit insurance and cost of operating fleet and other incidental charges
	Equipment (capital cost)	Purchase cost associated with the equipment necessary to the production
	Installation	Cost of installing the systems and equipment
	Maintenance	Cost of maintaining the production capacity of the facility and equipment
	Labour cost	Needed man-hours associated with production

Compilation of data from ViSS value chain members via tables that compile costs.

Purchase costs of raw materials (inputs) (assumption of purchase cost of raw materials)

Is there a purchase cost of raw materials at this stage? Yes/No

Input	Amount	Unit	Cost (€)	Concerned value chain stage	Observations
TOTAL			0		

Transport costs of materials (inputs - outputs)

Is there an associated transport cost of materials? Yes/No

Transport service	Service costs (€)	Service cost per ton	Observation
TOTAL	0		
Transport service	Service costs (€)	Service cost per ton	Observation

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Results: interim sustainability assessment

	Hydrolysis	Conditioning	Fermentation	Separation	PHBV production	Separation of PHBV	Drying	Solid-liquid extraction	Solvent recuperation	PHBV drying	Total per cost line
Raw material costs	1,45 €	347,48 €	- €	- €	65,17 €	- €	- €	94,21 €	- €	- €	508,41 €
Water	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Energy	4,07 €	1,00 €	10,00 €	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Carbon dioxide into the air - <i>Not included in the LCA</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Transport related costs (input-output)	70,00 €	- €	70,00 €	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Equipment, installation and amortization costs	2,98 €	115,38 €	- €	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Maintenance costs	- €	- €	- €	32,27 €	- €	2,62 €	5,24 €	- €	- €	- €	40,13 €
Labour costs	43,95 €	100,00 €	600,00 €	200,00 €	326,51 €	69,07 €	52,33 €	92,09 €	27,21 €	16,74 €	1527,90 €
Total conventional cost per process	122,45 €	563,86 €	680,51 €	232,27 €	795,48 €	84,55 €	77,33 €	190,53 €	29,48 €	97,28 €	2.873,74 €
Proportion of each process	4,3%	19,6%	23,7%	8,1%	27,7%	2,9%	2,7%	6,6%	1,0%	3,4%	100,0%
Environmental costs						25,00 €					

VISS LCC builds on the LCA with the objective of assessing the **conventional and environmental externality costs related** to the input and output included in the LCA model

Preliminary results

Missing monetisation of environmental externalities
(*environmental cost*)

No benchmark available

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ViSS ICT platform: Evaluation and Decision Tool

Aspect	Indicator	Score
Aspect 1	Indicator 1.1	4
	Indicator 1.2	4

Aspect 2	Indicator 2.1	4
	Indicator 2.2	3

...

Safety

Aspect	Indicator	Score
Aspect 1	Indicator 1.1	4
	Indicator 1.2	4

Aspect 2	Indicator 2.1	4
	Indicator 2.2	4

...

LCA

Aspect	Indicator	Score
Aspect 1	Indicator 1.1	4
	Indicator 1.2	4

Aspect 2	Indicator 2.1	4
	Indicator 2.2	3

...

So-LCA

Aspect	Indicator	Score
Aspect 1	Indicator 1.1	4
	Indicator 1.2	4

Aspect 2	Indicator 2.1	4
	Indicator 2.2	3

...

LCC

The challenge

SSbD is 4 dimensional: Safety | Environmental | Economic | Social

Yet methods exist only for:

✓ Safety, Environmental (LCA) ✗ Social & Economic

The opportunity

Social & economic assessment methods for SSbD are:

Scarce

Not harmonized

ViSS fill this gap by providing:

- Indicators
- Methodologies

Practical Implementation: the 0-4 scoring scale

Advantage:

Simple, intuitive scoring system (0-4) enables rapid assessment and stakeholder engagement

Caveat:

Simplification = information loss. Always pair quantitative scores with supporting contextual data.

What ViSS Demonstrates for SSbD

1. SSbD frameworks must be operationalized

Existing guidelines alone are insufficient. Real projects need concrete tools.

2. All three dimensions require equal attention

Social & economic methods are as critical as environmental ones for responsible innovation

3. Simplicity ≠ Superficiality

Accessible tools (like 0-4 scales) work best when backed by robust data & transparent methodology

Interactive workshop

Navigating Social Sustainability Across Polymer Production, Processing, and Agricultural Applications

15:50 – 16:00 | Alba Matamoros, Kveloce (**PHAntastic project**)

Social Hotspots identification methodology

Methodology

✓ Recommendations

S-LCA assessment

Social hotspots

Risks identification

VERY HIGH RISK
 HIGH RISK
 MEDIUM RISK

P·H·A Antastic

Product Context

Biodegradable PHA-based agricultural products (mulch films, growth foams) across Spain, Netherlands, Sweden, USA, China

Examples of social risks:

- Migration (S) — Labour mobility, migrant worker conditions, and transnational workforce impacts
- Nature (S) — Biodiversity, ecosystem health, and natural capital preservation
- Technology Development (S) — Innovation, process improvement, and technological advancement
- Freedom of Association and Collective Bargaining (W) — Right to organise, unionise, and negotiate collectively
- Forced Labour (W) — Prevention of coercion, trafficking, and involuntary work
- Corruption (VC) — Bribery, fraud, lack of transparency, and institutional integrity in business operations

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**Thanks for
your attention!!**

Alba Matamoros, Kveloce

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SESSION 4

**ADVANCED BIO-BASED POLYMERS:
PROCESSING, SCALE-UP
AND DIGITALISATION**

Polymers
2026

Advance Bio-Based Polymers: Processing, Scale-Up and Digitalisation

Guest Speakers:

Mrs. Beatriz Cardoso

Portugal

PhD in Materials Engineering
Junior researcher | University of Minho

Dr. Alejandra Pita

Spain

PhD in Chemistry
Senior Researcher | IDENER

Dr. Luis Mínguez

Spain

PhD in Materials Science
R&D | CETEC

Dr. Yannik Matt

Germany

PhD in Chemistry (KIT)
Lab Team Leader | BASF

About the Speakers

- **Mrs. Beatriz Cardoso, BIAL, Portugal (VINNY)**

Mrs. Beatriz Cardoso is a contracted junior researcher at the University of Minho, affiliated with the Centre of MicroElectroMechanical Systems (CMEMS). She holds a PhD in Materials Engineering (2023), an MSc in Biophysics and Bionanosystems (2018), and a BSc in Genetics and Biotechnology (2015), reflecting a multidisciplinary background across biology, materials science, and applied engineering.

Her research focuses on advanced nanoencapsulation and multi-stimuli-responsive delivery systems, green synthesis of nanomaterials, microfluidic and organ-on-chip platforms, with applications in biomedicine, sustainable agriculture, environmental technologies, and aerospace systems. She is currently a researcher in the European VINNY project, dedicated to the development of advanced nanoencapsulation strategies for bio-based pesticides and fertilizers, promoting circular and sustainable viticulture.

- **Dr. Luis Mínguez, CETEC, Spain (PHAntastic)**

Dr. Luis Mínguez-Enkovaara holds a PhD in Materials Science, with a research focus on polymer matrix nanocomposites, and a background in Industrial Engineering. He currently works as a Project Technician at CETEC and also lectures on Materials Science at the Technical University of Cartagena. His professional profile bridges industrial practice and research-oriented academic work.

- **Dr. Yannik Matt, BASF, Germany (REBIOLUTION)**

Dr. Yannik Matt holds a B.Sc. and M.Sc. in Chemistry from the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), followed by a PhD in Chemistry at KIT. His doctoral research focused on the development of building blocks for three-dimensional organic frameworks and included a research stay at the University of Edinburgh. Dr. Matt is currently working at BASF SE, where he serves as a Lab Team Leader specializing in polyaddition and polycondensation processes for specialty polymers. In addition to leading a team, he acts as Work Package Leader for Synthesis and Blending within the Rebiolution Project, driving innovation in advanced polymer materials.

- **Dr. Alejandra Pita Milleiro, IDENER, Spain (MAGNO)**

Dr. Alejandra Pita holds a PhD in computational chemistry and works as a Senior Researcher at IDENER, a Spanish RTO focused on applying AI across sectors to deliver more efficient and sustainable solutions. She is part of the coordination of the MAGNO project and leads the development of its digital twin.

Stimuli-responsive PLLA nanovesicles for controlled delivery of grape cane extracts in sustainable viticulture
Beatriz D. Cardoso

Nanoencapsulation: PLLA/PVA 1% + Grape cane extract (E1)

10 identified Polyphenols → 25 %

Grape cane biomass; pruning waste from *Vitis vinifera*

Mostly active against downy mildew

Double-emulsion (W1/O/W2) solvent evaporation method

Nanoencapsulation: PLLA/PVA 1% + Grape cane extract (E1)

Sample	PLLA (mg)	Extract	PVA
PLLA E1 1%	250	1% (2.5 mg)	1%
PLLA E1 5%	250	5% (12.5 mg)	1%
PLLA E1 10%	250	10% (25.0 mg)	1%

PVA
Water-soluble
Non-ionic surfactant

Mean size= 180 ± 21 nm

Nanoencapsulation: PLLA/PVA 1% + Grape cane extract

Encapsulation efficiency

$$EE (\%) = \frac{m_{\text{encapsulated extract}}}{m_{\text{total extract}}} \times 100$$

$$EL (\%) = \frac{m_{\text{encapsulated extract}}}{m_{\text{polymer}}} \times 100$$

Sample	EE % ± SD	EL % ± SD
PLLA E1 1%	78.2 ± 3.6	0.78 ± 0.03
PLLA E1 5%	89.0 ± 3.0	4.45 ± 0.15
PLLA E1 10%	92.2 ± 3.4	9.22 ± 0.34

- ✓ High EE values (>75–90%) indicate effective incorporation into PLLA
- ✓ Extract loading increased proportionally with initial extract content
- ✓ Loading increase does not plateau → the system is not saturated yet; load even more extract

Nanoencapsulation: PLLA/PVA 1% + Grape cane extract

Hydrodynamic size and stability

Vineyard environments exhibit **variable pH conditions**

pH values (5.5, 6.5, 7.5) simulate relevant agricultural conditions

Particle size remained consistent (<200 nm) across all formulations
→ reproducible nanoparticle formation

No significant size increase with higher extract loading → efficient incorporation without structural disruption

Low PDI (0.10) → uniform and well-dispersed nanoparticles

- Water
- ▨ pH 5.5
- ▩ pH 6.5
- pH 7.5
- PDI

Metabolic activity against *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* (resazurin reduction)

A. tumefaciens: Model pathogen for grapevine infections

Free extract → Sharp reduction in metabolic activity; dose-dependent

Encapsulated extract → slight increase in metabolic activity compared to free E1 → limited short-term bioavailability

Antibacterial activity against *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*

Overall, limited antibacterial activity observed (<1 log reduction)

Free E1 shows minimal and non-dose-dependent effect

A marked reduction observed at PLLA–E1 5% (~4.28 log)
 → absence of a consistent trend suggests a concentration-specific or condition-dependent effect

Metabolic activity against *Xylophilus ampelinus* (resazurin reduction)

Free extract → low metabolic activity

Encapsulated extract → higher metabolic activity than free extract

X. ampelinus: Key grapevine pathogen; necrosis in grapevine

Free extract → Sharp reduction in metabolic activity; dose-dependent

Encapsulated extract → slight increase in metabolic activity compared to free E1 → limited short-term bioavailability

Antibacterial activity against *Xylophilus ampelinus*

Antibacterial activity (\log_{10} CFU/mL reduction)

Control

E1 10%

PLLA E1 5%

PLLA E1 10%

Antibacterial activity is observed across all conditions (~2 log reduction)

Nanoencapsulated shows slightly higher activity than free extract

Antibacterial response is strain-dependent

Antifungal activity against *Botrytis cinerea*

B. cinerea: one of the most damaging fungal diseases in viticulture

Antifungal activity (% reduction)

✓ **PLLA E1 1%** showed significantly reduced growth compared to both control and free extract (E1 1%)

✓ **Encapsulated samples** showed significantly improved activity compared to **free extract E1 1%**

✓ **In PLLA systems:** improved interaction with fungal surface and sustained release of active compounds

Conclusions

Physicochemical properties

- ✓ **Successful formation of PLLA nanovesicles** (~180 nm, low PDI)
- ✓ **High encapsulation efficiency** (>75–90%)
- ✓ **Good stability** across relevant pH conditions
- ✓ Indicate suitability for **controlled delivery in viticulture environments**

Antibacterial Activity

- ✓ Antibacterial effect is **strain-dependent**
- ✓ **Limited activity against *Agrobacterium*** with variable response
- ✓ Consistent activity against ***X. ampelinus*** (~2–2.5 log reduction)
- ✓ Suggests controlled release behavior affects short-term efficacy

Antifungal Activity

- ✓ **Encapsulation improves activity** under specific conditions (1%)
- ✓ Free extract shows limited antifungal effect
- ✓ Indicates a **formulation-dependent response**
- ✓ Demonstrates potential of **nanosystems for fungal growth control**

TAKE-HOME MESSAGE

PLLA nanosystems enable **efficient encapsulation and stability** of biopesticides
Encapsulation **modulates antimicrobial activity** in a strain-dependent manner
Encapsulation enhances antifungal **activity against *Botrytis cinerea***

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Fernandes**

Principal investigator: Vinny

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Universidade do Minho

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Biobased plastics compounding: from lab to pilot scale

Speaker: Dr. Luis Minguez-Enkovaara

Funded by
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PHA-based mulch films for agriculture

- ✓ **Better plant growth** → optimal soil temperature + moisture retention.
- ✓ **Higher production** → All the nutrients are focused on crops, not weed.
- ✓ **Better crop development** → better root system.
- ✓ **Less use of herbicides** → the use of phytosanitary products is decreased.

Conventional plastics in agriculture

- ✓ Costs of plastics removal after crop cycle.
- ✓ Plastics accumulation in soil.
- ✓ Reduced soil efficiency for plant growth.

**Polymer coated fertiliser
(PE, EVA)**

**Mulch film
(LLDPE, LDPE, PLA)**

**Growth foams
(PU, PS)**

PHAs as a sustainable alternative

Advantages

- ✓ **Bio-based synthesis.**
- ✓ **Biodegradable properties in all media.**
- ✓ **Tunable properties and UV resistance.**

Challenges

- ❑ **Production cost.**
- ❑ **Processing parameters.**
- ❑ **Limited material availability.**

PHANTASTIC SOLUTION

PHA BLENDS:

- **100% Bio-based.** From agri-food wastes.
- **Biodegradable.** In all environments.
- **Non-toxic.** Safe for food use.

9 ACTIVE BIOPRODUCTS:

- **Bioactive products + microorganisms.**
- For Improved **soil health.**
- For **crop performance.**
- For faster **PHA degradability.**

Project requirements

Develop a manufacturing protocol for fully PHA-based blends
for mulch films

Fully PHA-based blend

- Includes PHBV produced within PHAntastic.
- SSbD compliant.

Mulch-film-capable properties

Compounding
by twin-screw extrusion

Blown-film extrusion processing

Development constraints

Fully PHA-based blend

- with PHBV produced within PHAntastic
- SSbD compliant

Mulch-film-capable properties

Compounding by **twin-screw** extrusion

Blown-film extrusion processing

- ¿PHBV percentage?
- Just 200 g of PHBV available for:
 - . Characterization.
 - . Blend screening.
 - . Characterization of blends.

- Tensile strength
- Elongation at break

- Minimum quantity of 300 g.

- At least 2 kg needed.
- Processability needs to be validated.

With only 200 g of PHBV, even a film-validated 10% blend is barely feasible.

Material screening

Produce fully PHA-based mulch films

1. Two PHBV grades produced within PHAntastic.

- **Medium HV grade.** PHBV with a 10 mol % HV

- **High HV grade.** PHBV with a 30 mol % HV

2. Commercial PHAs considered for blending.

Type PHA, % comonomer	Melting point (°C)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
PHBH, 6% 3HH (BP330-05)	148	34 – 38	≤ 5
PHBH, 10% 3HH (BP350-05)	132	25 – 29	≥ 10
P34HB, 10% 4HB (PB3420G)	170	20 – 25	≥ 10
P34HB, 15% 4HB (PB3430G)	170	10 – 15	>100
P34HB, 35% 4HB (A1000P)	135 – 170	5 – 7	>500
PHBV, 2% 3HV (Y1000P)	175-180	39	3.8
PHBV, 10% 3HV (CETBIO 10-15)	155	28	4
PHBV, 27.4% 3HV (CETBIO 20-30)	151	22	21
PHBV, >30% 3HV (CETBIO 20-30)	-	13	230

PHBH (3HB + 3HHx)

P34HB (3HB + 4HB)

PHBV (3HB + 3HV)

Our strategy

PHA-blends' screening
in micro-compounder

Validation of PHA-blend
by blown film

Development of
manufacturing protocol

Further biodegradation
trials for the project

1. Commercial BIOSOL material for mulch film as a reference.
2. Micro-compounding blend screening.
3. PHA blend validation by blown film extrusion.
4. Manufacturing protocol (compounding + blown-film extrusion).
5. Material supply to other tasks of the project.

Micro-compounder stage

PHA blends' screening at lab scale

Micro-compounding stage:

Advantages:

- ✓ **Low material needs.**
5 samples can be processed with just 15 gr.
- ✓ **Material samples to be characterized.**
Standardized samples for testing.
- ✓ **Comparable melt-processing conditions.**

Main outputs:

- Blend feasibility, 14 different blends were screened.
- Processing parameters guide.
- Material properties.

Methodology:

- Preparation of at least 5 samples/material
- Material characterization.

Results

PHA blends' screening at lab scale

Micro-compounding stage:

Reference commercial blends:

- Commercial **BIOSOL** as a reference for mulch film properties.
Ts: 20 MPa Eb: 347 %

Range of PHA properties:

	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)
CETBIO PHBV	20 - 30	4 - 21
PHBH	28 - 38	15 - 28
P34HB	4 - 18	170 - 1070

Results

Commercial blends processability

Commercial blends pre-validation by blown-film extrusion:

Proposed reference commercial PHA blends:

Blown-film processable

- REF C1. Based on commercial PHAs
- REF C2. Based on commercial PHAs
- REF C3. Based on commercial PHAs
- REF C4. Based on commercial PHAs

Results

PHA blends' screening at lab scale

Micro-compounding stage:

Reference commercial blends:

- REF C1 – Fully PHA-based blend
- REF C2 – Fully PHA-based blend

PHBV percentage selection:

- CETBIO(10-15) reached the best properties below 50 % additions.
- CETBIO(20-30) reached the best properties below 50 % additions.

Additional material

- 1,5 kg of both CETBIO PHBV grades produced for the rest of the validation.

Cast-film extrusion

Film processability at small scale

Film validation by cast-sheet extrusion:

Processability:

- REF C1 ✓
- CETBIO (10-15) REF ✓
- CETBIO (20-30) REF ✗
- BIOSOL ✓

Possible causes:

- Polymer immiscibility.
- Blend contamination from fermentation process.

Blend selection:

- CETBIO(10-15) showed the best processability and properties for mulch film.

Blown-film extrusion

Validation of film processability and properties

Film validation by blown-film extrusion

Potential enhancement of tensile strength with further bioactives incorporation and blend optimization.

Similar elongation at break to BIOSOL

Results comparison

Similar properties across different processing steps

Material properties after different processing steps:

Results:

- Processing BIOSOL at each stage validated the blends.
- Similar properties across micro-compounding, cast-film and blown-film.

Conclusions

1. A PHBV-based blend with comparable properties to mulch film was obtained.
2. Maintaining the same materials, validation of processability can be done between different processing technologies.
3. Micro-compounders offer a great solution in terms of material savings during development.
4. Further blend optimization needs to be carried out with both CETBIO (10-15) & CETBIO (20-30)-based blends.

Next steps

1. Further blend testing with CETBIO (20-30)-based blends.
2. Incorporation of bioactives into the blend matrix.
3. Production scale up.

Thanks for your PHAntastic attention!

<https://phantastic-project.eu/>

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Ecosystem Digital Twin for Circular Packaging Solutions: From Manufacturing to End of Life (MAGNO EU Project)

Dr. Alejandra Pita
alejandra.pita@idener.ai
IDENER

Introduction to MAGNO

- Project name (ID, budget): MAGNO (ID: 101135258, € 4M)
- Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-7 - Strategies to prevent and reduce plastic packaging pollution from the food system
- Project Start / End: 01/2024 – 06/2027
- Coordination: Dr. Alejandra Pita, Mr. Ignacio Fernández-Pacheco, Dr. Luis Acevedo
- Contact email: alejandra.pita@idener.ai
- Project Website: <https://magno-project.eu/>
- Project LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/magno-eu-project>

Introduction to MAGNO

The project focuses on the whole **food packaging value chain**, starting from raw materials production up to waste management – and back

Our goals are:

- Identify effects and impacts of food packaging **production, use** and **end of life**, with a particular focus on plastics
- Develop innovative **circular business strategies** and validate these with an **ecosystem Digital Twin**
- Include **public, private sectors** and **consumers** in food packaging system loop

MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

The project focuses on the whole **food packaging value chain**, starting from raw materials production up to waste management – and back

Our goals are:

- Identify effects and impacts of food packaging **production, use** and **end of life**, with a particular focus on plastics
- Develop innovative **circular business strategies** and validate these with an **ecosystem Digital Twin**
- Include **public, private sectors** and **consumers** in food packaging system loop

MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

Home

Value Chain Analysis

Auth Required

Register

Login

Plastic Food Packaging Value Chain Analysis

Select your Analysis Mode

Beginner Mode

Simplified interface with default values and step-by-step guides.

- ✓ Simplified forms
- ✓ Optimized default values

Advanced Mode

Full control over all technical parameters and settings.

- ✓ All parameters available
- ✓ Full control over configuration

Funded by
the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. MAGNO project has received funding from Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action programme under Grant Agreement n° 101135258.

Home

Value Chain Analysis

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Plastic Food Packaging Value Chain Analysis

← Back

Select Flow Type

Beginner

Circular Flow

Full lifecycle including recycling paths. Material is recovered and fed back into the value chain.

- Main path + recycling options
- Material recovery loop
- Sustainability-focused analysis

Linear Flow

End-to-end single-use lifecycle ending in disposal. No material is recovered.

- Straight-through discarding path
- Incineration, landfill, composting
- Impact assessment focus

Funded by
the European Union

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MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

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- Value Chain Analysis
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Value Chain Configuration

← Back Beginner Circular

1 Configure Value Chain Flow

Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path.

```
graph LR; PD[Product Design] --> RM[Raw Materials]; RM --> Mfg[Manufacturing]; Mfg --> LPM[Logistics Post-Mfg]; LPM --> Pkg[Packaging]; LPM --> LTR[Logistics To Retail]; LTR --> RSL[Retailer Shelf Life]; RSL --> USD[Use & Demand]; USD --> CSS[Collection & Sorting];
```

Recycling Path

- Mechanical Recycling
- Chemical Recycling

Recovery →

Instructions: Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path. Gray boxes are reference-only.

→ Proceed to Forms

MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

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Value Chain Configuration

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1 Configure Value Chain Flow

Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path.

```
graph LR; PD[Product Design] --> RM[Raw Materials]; RM --> M[Manufacturing]; M --> L1[Logistics Post-Mfg]; L1 --> P[Packaging]; P --> L2[Logistics To Retail]; L2 --> R[Retailer Shelf Life]; R --> UD[Use & Demand]; UD --> CS[Collection & Sorting]; CS --> RP[Recycling Path]; RP --> MR[Mechanical Recycling]; RP --> CR[Chemical Recycling]; MR --> RE[Recovery]; CR --> RE;
```

Instructions: Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path. Gray boxes are reference-only.

→ Proceed to Forms

MAGNO eDT: Product design

USER INPUTS

- Type of package
- Shape
- Main dimensions
 - Height
 - Base
 - Volume
- Thicknesses and layers
- Material

Product design
module of the DT

MODEL OUTPUTS

- Total mass
- Product (package) dataset of geometrical variables
 - External area
 - Useable volume
 - Gas product exchange area
 - Area/Volume relation
 - Other variables

MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

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Value Chain Configuration

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1 Configure Value Chain Flow

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```

Instructions: Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path. Gray boxes are reference-only.

→ Proceed to Forms

MAGNO eDT: Manufacture

Available manufacture processes:

- Injection molding
- Thermoforming
- Blow molding
- Extrusion molding

MAGNO's eDT: Manufacturing Module

- Beginners

- Home
- Value Chain Analysis
- Auth Required
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- Login

← Back Beginner Mode

Polymer Type Select a polymer... Selected once and applied to all modules (Manufacturing, EOL, Shelf Life, etc.)

Product Design **Manufacturing** Logistics (Post-Mfg) Mechanical recycling

Injection molding

Beginner Mode: You only need to fill in the basic fields. The remaining values will be automatically set with recommended defaults.

Manufacturing Country ? Polymer set globally above Volume & mass auto-injected from Product Design

Select a country...

Automatically Configured Parameters

Machine Power:	Ejection Temperature:	COP:
35 kW	25 °C	3

Calculate Results

MAGNO's eDT: Manufacturing Module

- Advanced

Home | Value Chain Analysis | Auth Required | RAG | admin@idener.ai | Logout

Back | **Advanced Mode**

Product Design | **Manufacturing** | Logistics (Post-Mfg) | Shelf Life | Incineration

Extrusion

Manufacturing Country Polymer type

Volume V (m³) Initial temperature T_I (°C)

Final temperature T_F (°C) Screw diameter D (m)

Flight depth H (m) Screw speed N (rev/s)

Pressure drop dP (Pa) Helix angle φ (rad)

Advanced parameters

COP <input type="text" value="3"/>	Shot volume V _{shot} (m ³) <input type="text"/>	Injection temperature T _{inj} (°C) <input type="text"/>
Ejection temperature T _{eject} (°C) <input type="text"/>	Latent heat H _f (kJ/kg) <input type="text"/>	Polymer mass m _{pol} (kg) <input type="text"/>
Moisture content (kg/kg) <input type="text" value="0.01"/>	SMER (kJ/kg) <input type="text" value="2450"/>	Trimming percentage (0-1) <input type="text" value="0.01"/>
Shear stress τ (Pa) <input type="text"/>	ΔH _f (kJ/kg) <input type="text" value="0"/>	Extrusion rate (m ³ /s) <input type="text"/>

Calculate Results

MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

- Home
- Value Chain Analysis
- Auth Required
- Register
- Login

Value Chain Configuration

← Back Beginner Circular

1 Configure Value Chain Flow

Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path.

The diagram shows a value chain flow with the following steps: Product Design, Raw Materials, Manufacturing (Click to select), Logistics (Post-Mfg), Packaging, Logistics (To Retail), Retailer (Shelf Life), Use & Demand, and Collection & Sorting. A dashed box highlights the 'Recycling Path' section, which includes Mechanical Recycling, Chemical Recycling, and a Recovery arrow.

Instructions: Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path. Gray boxes are reference-only.

→ Proceed to Forms

MAGNO's eDT: Transport Module

MAGNO eDT: Logistics

- Globally recognized methodology specifically developed for freight and logistics GHG accounting.
- Aligned with key international standards.
- Widely adopted by industry leaders.
- Covers all transport modes and logistics operations.
- Well-to-wheel (WTW) logic: Well-to-Tank (WTT) + Tank-to-Wheel (TTW)
- Extensive database.

Transport Chain Elements (TCEs)

MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

Home

Value Chain Analysis

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Login

Value Chain Configuration

← Back Beginner Circular

1 Configure Value Chain Flow

Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path.

The flowchart shows a sequence of steps: Product Design, Raw Materials, Manufacturing (highlighted with a dashed blue border and a dropdown arrow), Logistics (Post-Mfg), Packaging, Logistics (To Retail), Retailer (Shelf Life) (highlighted with a solid yellow border), Use & Demand, and Collection & Sorting. Below this, a dashed green box contains a 'Recycling Path' section with 'Mechanical Recycling' and 'Chemical Recycling' options, and a 'Recovery' arrow pointing right.

Instructions: Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path. Gray boxes are reference-only.

→ Proceed to Forms

MAGNO eDT: Shelf-life estimation

MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

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Value Chain Configuration

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1 Configure Value Chain Flow

Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path.

```
graph LR; PD[Product Design] --> RM[Raw Materials]; RM --> Mfg[Manufacturing]; Mfg --> LPM[Logistics Post-Mfg]; LPM --> Pkg[Packaging]; Pkg --> LTR[Logistics To Retail]; LTR --> RSL[Retailer Shelf Life]; RSL --> USD[Use & Demand]; USD --> CSS[Collection & Sorting]; CSS --> RP[Recycling Path]; subgraph RP; MR[Mechanical Recycling]; CR[Chemical Recycling]; end; RP -- Recovery --> RP;
```

Instructions: Click on **Manufacturing** to choose a process. Toggle optional steps and select one end-of-life path. Gray boxes are reference-only.

→ Proceed to Forms

MAGNO eDT: End-of-Life

MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

Home

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Product Design (Geometry) ANDORRA

Dimensions	
AVG THICKNESS	1.01 mm
LENGTH	202.0 mm
WIDTH	202.0 mm
HEIGHT	202.0 mm

Volumes & Areas	
USEFUL VOLUME	8.00 L
TOTAL SURFACE	0.245 m ²
INTERNAL AREA	0.240 m ²
SOLID VOLUME	0.24 L

Mass & Ratios	
MASS	0.242 kg
VIA RATIO	30.60 1/m

Material Flow

Per Unit	
POLYMER	
MASS / UNIT	0.242 kg
VOLUME / UNIT	8.00 L
SOLID VOL / UNIT	0.24 L
AREA / UNIT	0.245 m ²

Batch Totals	
NUMBER OF UNITS	100
TOTAL MASS	24.2 kg
TOTAL VOLUME	0.800 m ³

Injection ANDORRA

Energy Consumption	
TOTAL ENERGY	75.0 kJ
MELT	0.061 kJ
INJECTION	19.5 kJ
COOLING	40.4 kJ

Mass Balance	
MASS	0.242 kg
TOTAL MASS	0.238 kg
MOISTURE REMOVED	2.42 g
TRIMMED MASS	2.42 g

Process Parameters	
--------------------	--

MAGNO's Ecosystem Digital Twin

Upcoming Live Demonstration – Online!

MAGNO's eDT Online Workshop Coming Soon!

June 18th 2026 – Save the Date!

Project Website: <https://magno-project.eu/>

Project LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/magno-eu-project>

MAGNO

Transforming EU food systems with innovative
strategies for sustainable packaging

Funded by the
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Polymers
2026

SESSION 5

BIODEGRADATION IN OPEN ENVIRONMENTS: METHODS, APPLICATIONS AND ASSESSMENT

Polymers
2026

Biodegradation in Open Environments: Methods, Applications and Assessment

Guest Speakers:

Dr. Miriam Weber

Germany

PhD

Marine biologist and
co-directors |HYDRA Marine
Sciences GmbH

Dr. Marianna Kotzabasaki

Greece

PhD in Theoretical Chemistry and Drug
Design

Interdisciplinary Researcher | AUA

Dr. Yuanyuan Chen

Ireland

PhD in Biodegradable coronary stents
Senior Researcher | University TUS

About the Speakers

- **Dr. Miriam Weber, HYDRA Marine Sciences GmbH, Germany (REBIOLUTION)**

Dr. Miriam Weber is a marine biologist and co-directors of HYDRA Marine Sciences GmbH, Germany. Miriam studied in the USA, Australia and Germany and graduated at the Max Planck Institute for Marine Microbiology, Bremen. She attended dozens of research expeditions in lakes, rivers, and the sea, from high-alpine lakes to the Dead Sea, from the polar regions to the tropics, both in the Indo-Pacific and in the Atlantic Oceans. Her work focuses on developing solutions to pressing environmental problems. For the last 15 years she has been leading research on the biodegradation of plastic in the open environment with focus on the marine ecosystem, meanwhile also tackling freshwater and soil. Together with various partners from the EU, and in projects with public administrations, academia, private institutions, NGOs and industry the team has been developing and conducting tests in the field, in mesocosms and in the laboratory. Dr. Weber and her team has also been contributing to the introduction of several ISO standards on this matter and the SAPEA (Scientific Advice for Policy by European Academics) evidence review report on ‘Biodegradability of Plastic in the Open Environment’, metastudies, scientific per-reviewed articles, and media activities

- **Dr. Marianna Kotzabasaki, AUA, Greece (ANIPH)**

Interdisciplinary researcher with extensive experience across academia and the pharmaceutical industry, including roles in Quality Assurance (QA). Combines expertise in materials science—focused on nanobiomaterials and nanotechnology—with strong background in protein biotechnology, physicochemistry, and theoretical and computational chemistry. Applies advanced skills in materials modeling, drug design, cheminformatics, and machine learning to predictive nanotoxicology and sustainable agriculture challenges. Holds a PhD in Theoretical Chemistry and Drug Design from the University of Crete and completed postdoctoral research in machine learning–based nanotoxicology at the National Technical University of Athens.

- **Dr. Yuanyuan Chen, University TUS, Ireland (MAGICBIOMAT)**

Dr Yuanyuan Chen is a Principal Investigator (PI) in the Polymer, Recycling, Industrial, Sustainability and Manufacturing (PRISM) programme at the Technological University of the Shannon: Midlands Midwest (TUS). Her expertise includes biopolymer synthesis, processing, modification, degradation and recycling. She is currently coordinating a European consortium to programmable control the degradability of biopolymers (MAGICBIOMAT HE101181381), a European Innovation Council project in developing bio-based and biodegradable polyesters (Bio2PEs HE 101221903), and a Research Ireland & Horizon Europe co-funded project “Traceless” in developing biodegradable tree-supporting products (SF122/NCF/HE/1142).

Your strategy partner, turning insights into strategic advantages

Material Research & Customized Testing

Standard Tests for Soil, Marine & Freshwater

Visualization & Communication

Concepts & Consulting

contact:

Dr. Miriam Weber & Christian Lott

info@hydramarinesciences.com

https://hydramarinesciences.com/

Research & Test Center

Germany

Test your materials, products or demonstrators with us

in the lab, tank, and/or field.

(Soil, freshwater, marine & in transit)

Simulation tests in mesocosms

Biodegradability lab tests

recognized test lab PL340

Field tests

selected partners

selected public funding

“Biodegradation in the open environment: methodologies and gaps in standardisation”

Weber M¹ & Lott C¹

¹HYDRA Marine Sciences GmbH, Germany

**Marine
Sciences**

Dr. Miriam Weber, m.weber@hydramarinesciences.com

REBIOLUTION

POLICY,
LCA,
etc.

➔ baseline for
informed decisions

Waste hierarchy

Framework

All measures taken →

by e.g. redesign,
voluntary and enforced agreements,
EPR schemes,
regulations, laws,
infrastructure, management, etc.

Waste hierarchy

Framework

All measures taken →

by e.g. redesign,
voluntary and enforced agreements,
EPR schemes,
regulations, laws,
infrastructure, management, etc.

What are solutions for the **REST** ?

1961 – 2017 more than 1'500'000 FADs
(Fish Attracting Devices) abandoned
in the Mediterranean SEA

Sinopoli et al 2020

... have a high potential of loss to the environment
& will never be recollected.

... have unavoidable release to the environment,
and will never be recollected.

fibres lost from a wet wipe

... have unavoidable release to the environment,
and will never be recollected.

... put intentionally in the environment,
and will never be recollected.

...used in the environment
and loss will never be recollected, or recollection not foreseen

As we speak,
accumulation of
persistent materials in
the environment
continues, with
worrying impacts on
organisms, ecosystems
& humans.

Is Environmental Biodegradation a solution... for the problem of pollution?

HOW TO STRUCTURE, ASSESS & REGULATE ?
NEED FOR STRATEGIES, SCHEMES, OVERVIEWS

Yes, it is a solution for
specific applications & potentially as
last option for for unwanted leakage.

European policy on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics

Circular Economy
Action Plan

For a cleaner and
more competitive
Europe

Benefit:

REDUCTION OF POLLUTION of persistent plastic in the environment

Supporting actions towards a substitution with biodegradable plastics & polymers *where useful* should be applied.

Need for comparable test results

→ Standards & Testing schemes

Controllable and repeatable tests: **International Standards**

Standards are specifications and procedures to ensure reliability of services, materials, products, and/or **methods**.

- If available, we use them.
- If needed, we adapt them.
- If not available, we develop suggestions for new ones.

Example of a lab standard test on ISO level to proof

biodegradability

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD

ISO
22404

First edition
2019-09

Plastics — Determination of the
aerobic biodegradation of non-
floating materials exposed to marine
sediment — Method by analysis of
evolved carbon dioxide

Reference number
ISO 22404:2019(E)

© ISO 2019

End products of biodegradation:
Biomass, water and CO₂ or CH₄

Example of a field standard test on ISO level to assess erosion rates

Indirect measure: disintegration

e.g. benthic scenario: plastic sunk to the seafloor

3-tier test scheme for measuring biodegradation under most relevant conditions

Laboratory test

Proof of 'biodegradability'

- advantage:
 direct measurement
- criticism:
 not environmentally relevant

Field test

Assessment of disintegration in reality

- data of performance in nature
- *erosion rates for LCA, etc.*
- only indirect measurement
- uncontrolled conditions
- testing 'everywhere' is impossible

Tank test

Assessment of disintegration under conditions close to reality

- controlled
- *erosion rates for LCA, etc.*
- *easier access to more scenarios with relevant conditions*
- only indirect measurement

Peculiarities of the 3-tier test scheme

Lab tests: Use of the matrices sediment (e.g. sand) and water from the field test

➔ Link direct and indirect measurements

available biodegradation standards: **MARINE**

	Standard test methods: Pelagic zone (water column scenario)	Standard test methods: Benthic zone (seafloor scenario)	Standard test methods: Eulittoral zone (intertidal beach scenario)	Standards specifications	Related standards
Lab- oratory tests	ASTM D6691-2017 <small>under revision by ASTM WK82370</small>		ASTM D7991-2022	ASTM D7081-2005 <small>(withdrawn 2014) under renewal by ASTM WK75797</small>	ISO 5148:2022 <small>(DT50)</small>
	ASTM D6692-2001 <small>(w.d. 2010)</small>			ISO 22403:2020	ISO/AWI 18957 <small>(accel. test)</small>
	ISO 23977-1:2020	ISO 18830:2016	ISO 22404:2019		ISO 10210:2012/2022 <small>(sample prepr.)</small>
	ISO 23977-2:2020	ISO 19679:2020			ISO/CD 16623 <small>(matrice prepr.)</small>
Field tests	ISO 15314:2018	ISO 22766:2020	ISO 22766:2020		ASTM D6340-98(2007) <small>(withdrawn 2016)</small>
	ISO/CD 16636				CEN/TR 17910:2022
Tank tests	ISO 23832:2021	ISO 23832:2021	ISO 23832:2021		
		ASTM D7473/D7473M-21			

To do: anaerobic test

available biodegradation standards: **FRESHWATER**

	Standard test methods: Pelagic zone (water column scenario)	Standard test methods: Benthic zone (bottom scenario)	Standard test methods: Shore zone (bank scenario)	Standards specifications
Laboratory tests	ISO 14851:2019			
	ISO 14852:2021			
	ISO 14853:2016 (anaerobic)			
Field tests				
Tank tests				

**To do: lab tests with natural matrices
Field and tank tests**

available biodegradation standards: SOIL

	Standard test methods: Agricultural fields	Standard test methods: Forests	Standard test methods: Grassland, other relevant soils	Standards specifications
Laboratory tests	ASTM D5988-18 ISO 17556:2019	ISO 17556:2019	ISO 17556:2019	ISO 23517:2021 EN 17033:2018
Field tests				
Tank tests				

To do: Field and tank tests

WP4 T4.3 BIODEGRADATION IN **AQUATIC** ENVIRONMENTS: *OVERALL GOAL = ENVIRONMENTALLY RELEVANT TESTS IN AQUATIC SCENARIOS* (M5-36: HYDRA, BASF, OWS, ETHZ)

FRESHWATER

Focus on environmentally relevant test methods, like those available for marine scenarios

Goal

Validated test methods for freshwater scenarios

➔ *Motivation: Suggestions for standards & give policy recommendations*

WP4 T4.3 BIODEGRADATION IN AQUATIC ENVIRONMENTS:

TRANSFER: SOIL → FRESHWATER → MARINE; OXIC & ANOXIC

SCENARIO: Farmer using biodegradable mulch film

3 freshwater sediments:

- Small creek next to farmers fields
- Small lake next to farmers fields
- River where small creeks flow into

→ **Oxic conditions:** at sediment-water interface

→ **Anoxic conditions:** within sediment

One test material in 5 different environmental conditions

Samples

PHBH stick

Erosion rates

→ *Specific Surface Degradation Rates usable for LCA*

Conclusion:

If the material or product is biodegradable it will biodegrade, just at different speeds, depending on the environmental conditions, and material characteristics.

→ **WHAT TO RECOMMEND FOR TESTING REQUESTS BY POLICY?**

POLICY RECOMMENDATION

- ✓ Use optimized tests, ideally standards
- ✓ Report testing conditions according to protocol
- ✓ Aim for data usable in databases for LCA, PEF and other Risk Assessment tools (e.g. Specific Surface Degradation Rates)
- ✓ One test per ecosystem is enough

Your strategy partner, turning insights into strategic advantages

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Research & Test Center

Germany

Test your materials, products or demonstrators with us

in the lab, tank, and/or field.

(Soil, freshwater, marine & in transit)

Simulation tests in mesocosms

Biodegradability lab tests

recognized test lab PL340

Field tests

selected partners

selected public funding

- Cellulose filter paper biodegraded fast in most of the marine test scenarios, with half-lives of 2 weeks to 1 year
- In some treatments, biodegradation rates were low, probably due to lower temperature and nutrient content

➔ WHAT TO RECOMMEND FOR TESTING REQUESTS BY POLICY???

Cellulose filter paper under marine conditions

28 Mesocosm and Field Tests

Conclusion:

If the material or product is biodegradable it will biodegrade, just at different speeds, depending on the environmental conditions, and material characteristics.

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with us in the lab, tank, and/or field.

(Soil, freshwater, marine, and also in transit)

HYDRA
Research & Test Centre

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Midlands Midwest**

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Biodegradation of Polylactic acid

Dr Yuanyuan Chen

What is Polylactic acid

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- Bio-based polyester (from starch, corn, sugarcane)
- Thermoplastic (widely used in packaging, 3D printing)
- Good processability
- Moderate barrier/mechanical properties
- Compostable under industrial conditions

“Biodegradable” ≠ Real-World Degradable

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Industrial composting vs natural environments

- Requires ~58°C + high humidity (ISO 17088)
- Minimal degradation at ambient conditions

Slow degradation in:

- Soil
- Freshwater
- Marine

Mechanism of PLA Biodegradation

Two-step process:

1. Abiotic **hydrolysis**:

Ester bond cleavage → oligomers → lactic acid

2. Biotic assimilation:

Microorganisms convert lactic acid → $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$

Increase PLA Biodegradation strategy 1: polymer blending

Blend with more biodegradable polymers:

- PBAT
- PBS
- PHA
- Starch

Effects:

- Increased water uptake
- Reduced crystallinity
- Enhanced microbial access

Trade-offs:

- Mechanical property loss
- Phase compatibility issues

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Increase PLA Biodegradation strategy 2: additives & fillers

Natural fillers: plant fibre, Cellulose, lignin, starch
Plasticisers: Glycerol, PEG

Effects:

- Increase hydrophilicity
- Water uptake
- Create microvoids
- Accelerate hydrolysis
- Microbial colonisation

doi: [10.1021/acssuschemeng.3c04240](https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.3c04240)

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Increase PLA Biodegradation strategy 2: additives & fillers

Increase PLA Biodegradation strategy 2: additives & fillers

Increase PLA Biodegradation strategy 3: Enzymatic & Biological Approaches

Enzymes:

- Proteinase K
- Cutinases
- Lipases

Approaches:

- Surface treatment
- Enzyme embedding
- Bioaugmentation

Challenges:

- Stability
- Cost
- Activity in real environments

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Article | Published: 17 July 2024

An engineered enzyme embedded into PLA to make self-biodegradable plastic

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AI-Enabled Multi-Property Prediction of Biodegradability, Toxicological & Physicochemical Characteristics in PHA-Based Biopolymers

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¹ Agricultural University of Athens | ANIPH Project – H2020

Biopolymers

Machine Learning

Biodegradation

QSAR

PHAs

Why PHAs?

- Traditional plastics accumulate in all environmental compartments
- PHAs are bio-derived, truly biodegradable polymers — promising sustainable alternatives
- Demand growing across packaging, biomedical & agricultural sectors

The Bottleneck

Commercialisation requires simultaneously balancing biodegradability, physicochemical performance and toxicological safety → empirical testing is slow, costly and incomplete.

Biodegradability

Varies by environment (soil, marine, freshwater), additive load and chain length — hard to predict empirically

Physicochemical Properties

Thermal (T_g , T_m), mechanical (tensile) and rheological (viscosity) data are formulation-specific and sparse

Ecotoxicology & Cytotoxicity

Safety screening requires costly in-vitro assays; regulatory compliance (REACH/QSAR) demands documented evidence

End-to-end ML pipeline for PHA-based material property prediction

9 Validated & Deployed Predictive Models

- ✓ Tg & Tm (scl & mcl-PHAs)
- ✓ Tensile Strength (scl-PHA)
- ✓ Complex Viscosity (scl-PHA)
- ✓ Biodegradation % (scl-PHA)
- ✓ Ecotoxicity (scl-PHA)
- ✓ Cytotoxicity (scl-PHA)

Data Libraries – Curation & Scope

Data Scope

Materials

PHBV (scl-PHA) & mcl-PHA formulations with varied additives and building blocks

Biodegradation

Soil, freshwater & marine environments — experimental & literature data

Toxicology

Cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity assays across species and cell lines

Physicochemical

Thermal, mechanical and rheological property datasets

Curation Pipeline

1

Systematic Literature Mining

Scientific publications, technical reports, graphs and tables

2

Unit Harmonisation

Comparability ensured across sources

3

Outlier Detection & Removal

Improved data quality for model training

4

Normalisation & Encoding

Label/one-hot encoding for categorical variables

Physicochemical Property Models – Thermal & Mechanical

Random Forest Regressors | FAMD-engineered mixed descriptors | R^2 reported on test set

Tg - scl-PHA (PHBV)

Train R^2 :	0.983
Test R^2 :	0.875
CV R^2 (5-fold):	0.835

Tm - scl-PHA (PHBV)

Train R^2 :	0.969
Test R^2 :	0.866
CV R^2 (5-fold):	0.762

Tg - mcl-PHA

Train R^2 :	0.896
Test R^2 :	0.855
CV R^2 (10-fold):	0.800

Tm - mcl-PHA

Train R^2 :	0.945
Test R^2 :	0.916
CV R^2 (10-fold):	0.706

Tensile Strength

Train R^2 :	0.955
Test R^2 :	0.964
CV R^2 (10-fold):	0.826

Complex Viscosity

Train R^2 :	0.983
Test R^2 :	0.861
CV R^2 (10-fold):	0.854

Key SHAP drivers: monomer composition ratios (3HB & mcl-PHA fractions), additive type and loading, processing temperature

Biodegradation Model

Biodegradation %
scl-PHA (PHBV)

0.997
Train R²

0.980
Test R²

0.977
CV R² (10-fold)

Model Features

- ✓ Monomer composition (3HB, 3HV, mcl fractions)
- ✓ Additive type, loading & processing parameters
- ✓ Biodegradation medium (soil / freshwater / marine)
- ✓ Exposure duration and environmental conditions

⚠ Critical Data Gap & Our Response

Publicly available biodegradation data for mcl-PHA formulations were negligible — standard databases provided insufficient coverage for reliable ML modelling.

- ✓ AUA Response: We generated novel experimental biodegradation datasets for mcl-PHA materials in-house, enabling construction of a dedicated, reliable database where none existed.

Toxicological Safety Models – Ecotoxicity & Cytotoxicity

Ecotoxicity (scl-PHA)

Train	Balanced Acc. 0.948	macro-F1 0.947
Test	Balanced Acc. 0.937	macro-F1 0.933
CV 5-fold	Balanced Acc. 0.811	macro-F1 0.802

SHAP Insight: Species-related features (Terrestrial Plants, Air-Breathing Animals) were the strongest drivers of ecotoxicity predictions.

Cytotoxicity (scl-PHA)

Train	Balanced Acc. 0.929	macro-F1 0.929
Test	Balanced Acc. 0.954	macro-F1 0.938
CV 5-fold	Balanced Acc. 0.811	macro-F1 0.793

SHAP Insight: Additive_2 percentage was the dominant driver of cytotoxicity; incubation time and concentration showed clear dose- and time-dependent effects.

Deployment – Jaqpot Platform & Open Science

All 9 Models Deployed on Jaqpot | app.jaqpot.org

Tg – PHBV

Regression

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2299/description>

Tm – PHBV

Regression

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2300/description>

Biodegradation % – PHBV

Regression

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2324/description>

Tensile Strength – PHBV

Regression

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2321/description>

Complex Viscosity – PHBV

Regression

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2291/description>

Cytotoxicity – PHBV

Classification

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2259/description>

Ecotoxicity – PHBV

Classification

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2244/description>

Tg – mcl-PHA

Regression

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2322/description>

Tm – mcl-PHA

Regression

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2297/description>

github.com/FSL-AUA/ANIPH-models | Fully open-source workflows

Why This Matters

- ✓ Rapid in-silico screening without costly experiments
- ✓ REACH regulatory compliance by design
- ✓ Transparent & interpretable (SHAP assessment)
- ✓ Supports SSbD (Safe & Sustainable by Design) workflows
- ✓ Accelerates circular & sustainable polymer development

- 1 A novel multi-property ML framework was developed and validated for PHA-based biopolymers, covering biodegradability, physicochemical and toxicological endpoints in a single integrated pipeline.
- 2 9 Random Forest- based models achieve high predictive performance (test R^2 up to 0.98 for biodegradation; balanced accuracy up to 0.95 for toxicity classifiers).
- 3 SHAP analysis provides mechanistic insight into key formulation drivers, supporting interpretable and regulatory-compliant (REACH/QSAR) predictions.
- 4 In-house experimental biodegradation data for mcl-PHAs filled a critical literature gap, enabling reliable modelling where none was previously possible.
- 5 All models are openly deployed on the Jaqpot platform, providing the community with fast, reproducible decision-support for sustainable material design.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

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